

Master Thesis

1 October 2022 – 31 March 2023

Performance prediction of mercury ejector vacuum pumps as main component of the DEMO torus booster pumping system

by
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Master Thesis for

Mr. B. Sc. Clément Racinet (Matriculation # 2430793)

Performance prediction of mercury ejector vacuum pumps as main component of the DEMO torus booster pumping system

The operation of a DT fusion power plant requires the continuous vacuum pumping of the exhaust gas from the torus. The torus vacuum pumping system of the European demonstration fusion power plant (DEMO) is a serial arrangement of different pump types, with stages of high vacuum pumping, intermediate pumping and rough pumping with compression to ambient. To be tritium-compatible, all pump technologies of each pump train are based on the liquid metal mercury as operating fluid.

This thesis shall focus on the intermediate pumping stage that compresses and carries the gas from the outlet of the primary pumping system (vapour diffusion pumps) to the inlet of the roughing pump system (liquid ring pumps). Here, methods of describing these intermediate stage – single- and multi stage vapour jet vacuum pumps (ejector pumps) – shall be reviewed starting with a systematic literature review. The governing operation parameters of such pumps have to be identified. Based on the findings, a modelling procedure shall be developed for which the usability of computational fluid dynamics is to be assessed. The modelling approach has to be verified against literature data. A variation of the boundary condition values shall be performed to reveal operational and applicability limits (e.g. max. achievable compression rates or inlet/outlet pressures).

The modelling results shall then be exploited to demonstrate potential improvements to the current architecture of the DEMO pumping trains. Particular focus shall be given to the integration of vapour jet stages into the diffusion pumps and the trade-off between the number of vapour jet pumps and the number of rough pump stages. The thesis will evolve along the following steps:

- (i) Familiarization with the DEMO torus vacuum pumping system (Weeks 1 and 2)
- (ii) Literature survey on ejector vacuum pumps (W 3 to 6)
- (iii) Elaboration of calculation/modelling methods (W 7 to 10)
- (iv) Run calculations, benchmark with literature or experiments if available (W 11 to 14)
- (v) Investigate boundary conditions for vapour jet vacuum pumps (W 15 to 18)
- (vi) Demonstration of potential improvements of the DEMO vacuum pumping system (W 19 to 22)
- (vii) Completion of thesis writing (W 23 to 26)

The work will be carried out at the ITEP at the KIT Campus Nord. The Master thesis shall be written in English language and shall comprise a clear and concise depiction of the work that has been carried out. The results of the work shall be presented orally at the Institute's Colloquium.

Start of the work: 1. October 2022

Delivery of the work: 31. Mar 2023

Examiner: Prof. Dr.-Ing. Robert Stieglitz (IATF)Supervisor: Dr.-Ing. Thomas Giegerich (ITEP)Candidate: Clément Racinet

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DECLARATION OF OWN WORK

I truthfully declare that I have written this thesis independently, that I have indicated all the aids used completely and accurately, and that I have indicated everything that has been taken from the work of others, either changed or with modifications, and that I have observed the KIT Statutes for the Safeguarding of Good Scientific Practice in the currently valid version.

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Abbreviations

Notation	Meaning
1-D	One-dimensional
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
DEMO	Demonstration Fusion Power plant
DIRL	Direct Internal Recycling Loop
FVM	Finite Volume Method
ITEP	Institute for Technical Physics
ITER	International Thermonuclear Experimental Reactor
INTL	Inner Tritium Plant Loop
KIT	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology
Kn	Knudsen Number
LDP	Linear Diffusion Pump
LRP	Liquid Ring Pump
Ma	Mach Number
MFP	Metal Foil Pump
NXP	Nozzle X-axis Position (axial distance between nozzle and mixing chamber)
OUTL	Outer Tritium Plant Loop
RANS equations	Reynolds Averaged Navier-Stokes equations
Z	Atomic Number

Quantities Notation

Notation	Standard Unit	Meaning
A	[m ²]	Area
c	[m s ⁻¹]	Light celerity
c_p	[J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹]	Isobaric molar heat capacity
c_v	[J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹]	Isochoric molar heat capacity
d	[m]	Diameter
E	[J]	Energy
g	[m s ⁻²]	Earth gravitational constant
Kn	[-]	Mach number
L	[m]	Length
Ma	[-]	Mach number
M	[kg mol ⁻¹]	Molar mass
m	[kg]	mass
\dot{m}	[kg s ⁻¹]	Mass flow rate
P	[Pa]	Pressure
R	[J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹]	Perfect gas constant
R*	[J K ⁻¹ kg ⁻¹]	Specific gas constant
T	[K]	Temperature
t	[s]	Time
u	[-]	Entrainment ratio
v	[m s ⁻¹]	Velocity
x	[-]	Molar fraction
z	[-]	Compressibility ratio
Z	[-]	Atomic number
γ	[-]	Heat capacity ratio
ε	[K]	Lennard-Jones characteristic energy
η	[-]	Efficiencies
κ	[W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]	Heat conductivity
λ	[m]	Free mean path
μ	[Pa s]	Dynamic viscosity
ρ	[kg m ⁻³]	density
σ	[m]	Lennard-Jones characteristic length
τ	[-]	Diameter ratio
χ	[-]	Pressure ratio
ψ	[-]	Compression ratio

Index notations

Notation	Meaning
0	at the inlet
d	In the diffuser (after the second shock wave)
c	At the outlet
C	characteristic
cc	At the critical point
cb	At the breaking point
m	mixed fluid
p	primary fluid
s	secondary fluid
t	at the nozzle throat
y	at the y-y section

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Abstract

A continuous pumping solution for a fusion reactor is currently being developed at the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT). This allows the tritium inventory to be drastically reduced compared to current discontinuous pumping systems based on cryogenic pumps. In this concept, a mercury diffusion pump is used as the high vacuum pump and a liquid ring pump, also with mercury as the operating liquid, as the backing pump. Mercury is used because of its good tritium compatibility. However, as things stand at present, the suction pressure of the backing pumps and the delivery pressure of the diffusion pumps are not compatible. A considerable pressure difference must therefore be bridged to connect these two types of pumps. Ejector pumps have been identified as a possible pumping solution for this pressure difference. These pumps can also be operated with mercury as the primary fluid to ensure compatibility with tritium.

This work investigates whether and how such a pump can be used for the purpose described above. For this purpose, a new 1D model is first developed based on literature models. This model can be used to derive a pre-design for ejector pump stages quickly and cheaply. Subsequently, this design can be validated and optimised by 3D simulations using the finite volume method. Since ejectors in industry are typically used with identical operating and process media (usually steam), existing models are based on this assumption. One of the key points of the present work is therefore the extension of both 1D and 3D models to gas mixtures. The extended models are validated with literature data, in particular also with mercury as working medium.

Finally, the new 1D model is used to propose a functional, multi-stage solution for the pumping system and to show potential optimisations regarding the required number of ejector and ring pump stages. Furthermore, the 3D finite volume model is used as an example to quantify the accuracy of the 1D model.

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Zusammenfassung

Am Karlsruher Institut für Technologie (KIT) wird derzeit eine kontinuierliche Pumplösung für einen Fusionsreaktor entwickelt. Diese erlaubt es das Tritiuminventar im Vergleich zu gegenwärtigen, diskontinuierlichen Pumpsystemen, die auf Kryopumpen basieren, drastisch zu reduzieren. Bei diesem Konzept wird eine Quecksilberdiffusionspumpe als Hochvakuumpumpe und eine Flüssigkeitsringpumpe, ebenfalls mit Quecksilber als Betriebsflüssigkeit, als Vorvakuumpumpe verwendet. Quecksilber wird aufgrund seiner guten Tritiumkompatibilität verwendet. Allerdings sind nach derzeitigem Stand der Saugdruck der Vorvakuumpumpen und der Förderdruck der Diffusionspumpen nicht kompatibel. Es muss also eine nicht unerhebliche Druckdifferenz überbrückt werden, um diese beiden Pumpentypen miteinander zu verbinden. Ejektorpumpen wurden als mögliche Pumplösung für diese Druckdifferenz identifiziert. Auch diese Pumpen können mit Quecksilber als Primärfluid betrieben werden, um die Kompatibilität mit Tritium zu gewährleisten.

Das Ziel dieser Arbeit ist es zu untersuchen, ob und wie eine solche Pumpe zu dem oben beschriebenen Zweck eingesetzt werden kann. Zu diesem Zweck wird zunächst ein neues 1D Modell auf der Basis von Literaturmodellen entwickelt. Dieses Modell kann dazu verwendet werden ein Pre-Design für Ejektor-Pumpstufen schnell und kostengünstig abzuleiten. Anschließend kann dieses Design durch 3D-Simulationen mit der Finite-Volumen-Methode validiert und optimiert werden. Da Ejektoren in der Industrie typischerweise mit identischen Betriebs- und Prozessmedien (in der Regel Dampf) eingesetzt werden, sind vorhandene Modelle auf dieser Annahme aufgebaut. Einer der Schlüsselpunkte der vorliegenden Arbeit ist daher die Erweiterung von sowohl 1D als auch 3D Modellen auf Gasmischungen. Die erweiterten Modelle werden mit Literaturdaten validiert, insbesondere auch mit Quecksilber als Arbeitsmedium.

Abschließend wird das neue 1D Modell dazu verwendet, um eine funktionale, mehrstufige Lösung für das Pumpsystem vorzuschlagen und potentielle Optimierungen hinsichtlich der erforderlichen Zahl an Ejektor- und Ringpumpstufen aufzuzeigen. Außerdem wird das 3D Finite-Volumen Modell exemplarisch dazu verwendet die Genauigkeit des 1D Modells zu quantifizieren.

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1 Introduction to fusion

1.1 The necessity of nuclear fusion

The ability of humans to use energy, starting with the mastery of fire, is one of the factors that has permitted human evolution [1]. Since then, the human population has continued to consume more energy, and reaches a current consumption never equalled in the past (Fig. 1).

This level of consumption has led to current concerns about resource availability and the unfavourable effects of such a high usage of fossil fuels [3]. Indeed, our civilization is currently dependent on our energy sources. Determining how to diversify and maintain our energy sources is therefore essential.

Arthur Eddington conducted a conference at the British Association for the Advancement of Science's

annual meeting in Cardiff in 1920, in the midst of the industrial revolution and at a period when energy consumption had never been so high. He used Albert Einstein's famous equation (equation 1.1-1) which link the energy E to the mass m with the square of the speed of light c as proportionality factor to explain how stars are lighting by fusing hydrogen atoms:

$$\Delta E = \Delta m \cdot c^2 \quad 1.1-1$$

Eddington declared during the talk: "A star is drawing on some vast reservoir of energy by means unknown to us. This reservoir can scarcely be other than the subatomic energy which, it is known exists abundantly in all matter; we sometimes dream that man will one day learn how to release it and use it for his service. The store is well-nigh inexhaustible, if only it could be tapped" [4].

After more than a century of scientific study, the need for and likelihood of realizing Eddington's vision are greater than ever. If nuclear fusion could be controlled, we could use vast amounts of energy without releasing greenhouse gases that contribute to global warming.

1.2 Physics background on nuclear fusion

An atomic nucleus' mass is smaller than the combined masses of the nucleons that make it up. According to the mass-energy equivalence (equation 1.1-1), this mass defect is equivalent to a binding energy; it is zero for protium (1_1H), i.e., a single proton, and increases with the mass number (the number of nucleons) - initially very quickly and then more gradually up to iron (atomic number $Z=56$), and then slowly decreases (see Fig. 2). Nuclear fission, which occurs when a heavy nucleus ($Z>56$) is successfully split by a nuclear reaction, releases energy (currently used in nuclear reactors). Although

Fig. 1: Global direct primary energy consumption. Taken from [2].

relatively easy to realize technically, this reaction has significant downsides, most notably the quantity of radioactive waste it produces and necessary safety measures against a potential runaway reaction. On the other hand, fusion technology involves that two atomic nuclei must interpenetrate in order for a nuclear fusion reaction to occur. The nuclei must overcome the strong repulsion caused by their opposing positive electric charges in order for this to occur (the so-called "Coulomb barrier"). Due to the extraordinarily high microscopic kinetic energy (equivalent to the thermal agitation) required to breach the barrier, the likelihood of achieving the fusion of the nuclei would be exceedingly low if one employed solely the equations of classical mechanics. However, tunnelling can also break through the Coulomb barrier at lower energies, as predicted by quantum mechanics and demonstrated in practice [5, 6]. Depending on the composition of the nuclei, the energy needed for fusion remains extremely high and corresponds to temperatures of many tens or even hundreds of million Kelvin [7]. Under these conditions, the fuel will be in a plasma state confined by toroidal magnetic fields. As depicted in Fig. 3, the fusion reaction detailed in equation 1.2-1 between Deuterium $D = {}^2_1H$ and Tritium $T = {}^3_1H$ is the easiest to achieve. Furthermore, high-level, long-lived radioactive waste is not inherently produced by the nuclear fusion reaction. Depending on the materials selected for the first wall, the activation of fusion reactor components is anticipated to be low enough that the materials can be recycled or utilized again within 100 years of the plant being shut down [5, 8]. Thus, fusion has many advantages over other forms of energy: for a given mass, the energy released by the fusion of light atoms is nearly four times greater than that released by nuclear fission reactions and four million times greater than that of chemical reactions like the combustion of coal, oil, or gas [5].

1.2-1

Fig. 2: Binding energy per nucleon depending on the number of nucleons, adapted from [4].

Fig. 3: Fusion reactivity depending on the temperature, taken from [9].

1.3 Tritium self-sufficiency for the European Demonstration Fusion Power Plant (DEMO)

Deuterium, being available in water, is not a constraint. With tritium, the supply is more challenging. Tritium must be meticulously monitored and managed since it is a radioactive element utilized in nuclear weapons. Its price (in the order of \$30 000 per g) [10] is very high and its availability is very low due to the fact that it is generated only by artificial means and that it has a half-life of only 12.3 years which naturally decreases the amount available. Current stock levels, depicted in Fig. 4, are barely adequate for the intended use of the International Thermonuclear Experimental Reactor (ITER), which is now being constructed in Cadarache, France. As a result, future fusion reactors will need to produce their own tritium in order to be tritium-self-sufficient. The idea is to employ a blanket. This serves a number of purposes, including absorbing the energy of the neutrons produced during the nuclear fusion of deuterium and tritium (D-T), and it also enables the production of extra tritium, which would otherwise be difficult to obtain in sufficient quantities. To achieve that goal, the neutrons' react with the lithium isotopes ${}^6\text{Li}$ and ${}^7\text{Li}$ present in the blanket could be used (see equations 1.3-1 and 1.3-2). Thus, future nuclear fusion projects and in particular DEMO, the European successor to ITER and the project on which this study focuses will have to be self-sufficient in tritium. DEMO aims to demonstrate that it will be possible to produce electricity industrially using nuclear fusion technology and thus opens the way to the first European industrial nuclear fusion reactors.

Fig. 4: Tritium resources available for fusion reactors, taken from [11].

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2 Vacuum and tritium cycle

2.1 The DEMO fuel cycle

In order to achieve optimal fusion conditions, the plasma must be maintained at high purity. So, to ensure the minimal presence of contaminants and to exhaust the fusion product helium, the torus must be continuously pumped to a fine vacuum pressure [12]. However, as previously stated, tritium is very expensive and restricted due to its hazardous nature. As a result, tritium in the exhaust gas must be entirely recycled. Without significant alterations to the fuel cycle design, scaling up from ITER to a commercial reactor would result in a tritium inventory of more than ten kilograms [13], which is seen as a show-stopper for such a machine (safety, licencing and availability problems). To solve this problem, a 3-loop fuel cycle design was developed to minimize the amount and duration of tritium inventory build-up (see [Fig. 5](#)) [13]. Metal Foil Pumps (MFP) are used to separate unburnt D-T fuel from the exhaust gas mixture [14]. It is projected that 80% of the D-T in the exhaust stream will be recycled by the Direct Internal Recycling Loop (DIRL). The remaining 20% can be recycled in a second loop called Inner Tritium Plant Loop (INTL). This second loop is slower, but will allow for an exhaustive separation of the isotopes. Finally, a third and last loop, the Outer Tritium Plant Loop (OUTL) is planned to carry out various tasks that are not part of the recycling of elements present in the tokamak. In particular, this loop will handle the production of tritium from the lithium blankets and will serve as an active air detritiation circuit to ensure that the system is perfectly sealed.

2.2 The DEMO torus pumping system

At present fusion devices, cryogenic pumps are used as primary vacuum pumps in order to achieve the high vacuum required. This type of pumps works in the following way: walls cooled to a very low temperature are used to catch the particles that come into contact with them [15]. Thus, cryogenic pumps accumulate the pumped material and require a regeneration time in order to release it. This phenomenon generates a significant increase in the tritium inventory. In order to pump continuously and to limit the storage of tritium as much as possible, the idea of a non-cryogenic pumping system is followed (some examples are given in [16]). Because mercury is perfectly tritium compatible, a pumping system based on mercury pumps is currently being developed as shown in [Fig. 6](#). The primary pumps are mercury-driven Linear Diffusion Pumps (LDPs) which can reach the high vacuum required. These are backed by also mercury-driven Liquid Ring Pumps (LRPs) which work at higher pressure and compress to ambient [17–19].

Fig. 5: Systematic illustration of interlink between residence time and tritium inventory in the three-loop fuel cycle, taken from [13].

Fig. 6: Example of a mercury pumping system for DEMO, taken from [17].

2.3 The intermediate pumping stage (Booster Pump)

As we can see in Fig. 7 one stage of a LRP as expected for DEMO can only achieve around 20 000 Pa inlet pressure. With several stages of LRP in series, an ultimate pressure of 400 Pa would be achievable [20]. On the other hand, as shown in Fig. 8, one stage of LDP can reach outlet pressures of about 1 Pa before their performance declines. Using 3 stages in a LDP, it is believed that outlet pressures of 10 Pa could be achieved [20]. Therefore, there is a gap between the highest expected outlet pressure of the LDPs and the lowest achievable inlet pressure of the LRP. In order to cover the pressure gap between the LDP and the LRP, a new type of pump should be found. Knowing that for each additional pumping stage, the number of LRP required increases drastically, reach a LRP inlet pressure of 1 000 Pa would reduce the number of LRPs by 35 %, rise to 2 500 Pa would reduce it by more than 55% and achieving 7 000 Pa would reduce this number by more than 75%. Since LRPs are linked to space needs and complex maintenance work, limiting the number of LRPs would be ideal. The purpose of this study is to determine whether this goal can be reached by mercury powered ejector pumps in order to have a complete and effective pumping system for DEMO.

Fig. 7: Mercury liquid ring pump pumping curve for one stage, taken from [21].

Fig. 8: Mercury diffusion pump pumping curve for one stage, taken from [19].

3 Ejector vacuum pumping basics

3.1 Description of the working principle

Ejectors are device without moving parts that may pump, compress, or mix gases, vapours, or liquids due to the expansion of a primary fluid. The primary fluid supplies the momentum required to propel the secondary fluid. In our case, the primary fluid would be mercury vapour, while the secondary fluid is the exhaust gas mixture being pumped. A primary nozzle and a secondary nozzle are part of a traditional ejector. The latter consists of a diffuser and a receiving chamber with a constant section to ensure the mixing of the two fluids. The primary nozzle of a gas ejector is convergent-divergent (e.g. de Laval type) to produce a supersonic primary jet at its exit i.e. that its Mach Number Ma (function of the velocity v , the isentropic coefficient γ , the specific gas constant R^* and the temperature T) is greater than 1:

$$Ma = \frac{v}{\sqrt{\gamma R^* T}} \quad 3.1-1$$

The basic working principle of an ejector pump is displayed in Fig. 9: the primary fluid (in our case mercury vapour) enters the primary nozzle at high pressure, and its energy is subsequently transformed into kinetic energy by expansion. Due to the Venturi effect, the static pressure of this primary fluid jet drops down, which entrains the secondary fluid (in our case the exhaust gas mixture). The entrainment ratio u is defined as the ratio of the secondary mass flow rate (\dot{m}_s) to primary mass flow rate (\dot{m}_p) (see equation 3.1-2). The two fluids mix uniformly in the mixing chamber. In the diffuser, the velocity of the mixture is reduced, converting part of its kinetic energy to static pressure. The outlet pressure of the mixture lies between the primary and secondary inlet pressures, so the ejector has provided a compression of the entrained gas [22–24].

$$u = \frac{\dot{m}_s}{\dot{m}_p} \quad 3.1-2$$

Fig. 9: Schematic view and the variation of fluids pressure and velocity as a function of location along the ejector Inspired by [25].

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3.2 Discussion of operating conditions for standard vapour ejector pumps

Thereafter, in order to fit in with the need for DEMO (see section 2), we will focus on vapour ejector pumps i.e. ejectors operating with gases as primary and secondary fluid.

The three vapour ejector functioning modes are also depicted in [Fig. 10](#) [22, 25, 26]:

- 1- Critical mode: the entrainment ratio is constant and maximum as long as $P_c < P_{cc}$. In this mode, the primary fluid as well as the secondary fluid chock. The primary fluid chokes in the primary nozzle throat and the secondary fluid chokes in the mixing chamber. A shock wave to return to the subsonic regime appears in the diffuser (this is the case shown in Fig. 9).
- 2- Subcritical mode: the entrainment ratio drops down linearly with P_c between P_{cc} and P_{cb} . In this transition phase, only the primary fluid chokes in the primary nozzle throat. However, its energy is sufficient to counter completely the outlet pressure. The system continues to pump but in a degraded way.
- 3- Back-flow mode: The pumping action ceases (the pump will discharge through the secondary inlet), the entrainment ratio is then negative. In this case, the primary fluid has no longer enough energy to sustain against the outlet pressure. Leakage occurs and the outlet fluid can flow back through the secondary inlet.

Then, two essential points can be highlighted:

- the breakdown point, where $u = 0$ and the backing pressure P_c is equal to the breakdown backing pressure P_{cb} . This point is reached when the primary jet can no longer sustain against the outlet pressure.
- the critical point, where entrainment ratio u equals critical (and maximum) entrainment ratio and backing pressure P_c equals critical backing pressure P_{cc} . This point corresponds to the transition point where the mixed fluid ceases to shock in the diffuser.

The boundary conditions have of course a very high influence on the working point of the pump. To perfectly constrain the pump, there are 5 degrees of freedom used as boundary conditions. Usually (also in this study), the primary and secondary inlet pressure and temperature added to the outlet pressure constitute the boundary conditions. Their effect on the pump is huge but well understood and, hence, predictable. In fact, as long as one remains in critical mode the mass flow rate of the primary fluid is linearly dependant on the primary pressure (see in section 4.2.1 below) and the secondary mass flow rate is directly proportional to the latter (u is constant in critical mode). On the other hand, the influence of the primary pressure affects the mass flow of the secondary fluid in a much more complex way. However, the influence of the secondary and primary pressures and temperature on the mass flow ratio versus outlet pressure curve always evolve in the same way (see Fig. 10), which makes it possible to adjust these parameters as best as possible according to the final needs once the pump has been dimensioned.

Fig. 10: Global variation of entrainment ratio and critical point as function of the primary and secondary pressures and temperatures. Inspired by [26].

3.3 Main geometrical parameters influencing the pumping performance

Many different types of ejector designs exist, especially regarding the type of nozzle used. Some have two, three or more nozzles in series and/or in parallel. We will concentrate ourselves on the simplest version as the one shown in Fig. 11.

Although the geometry of such an ejector pump is relatively simple, it still has several important parameters that determine the pump performance. Because of the number of parameters, it is important to have numerical tools with which one can perform parameter scans so as to understand their impact on the overall performance. Computational Fluid Dynamics software (CFD) is able to describe the flows in such pumps parametrically without having to manufacture and test a lot of these pumps in experiments. Despite this, each calculation made by CFD costs a lot in terms of computational time. In order to limit these costs and knowing that a lot of research on the sensitivity of these parameters has been done in the past, summarizing previous research [24, 27–32], it can be concluded that the most important parameters affecting the ejector performance are the three following ones:

- The diameter ratio $\tau = \frac{d_m}{d_t}$
- The distance between primary nozzle mouth and mixing chamber (NXP) as shown on Fig. 11
- The dimensionless mixing length $\frac{L_m}{d_m}$

In the present work, we focus on these parameters during the geometrical sensitivity study.

Fig. 11: Main geometrical parameters in the design of a vacuum ejector.

4 Modelling of ejector pumps

4.1 State-of-the-art in ejector pump modelling

In literature, two main types of simulations for ejectors are employed. The first type is a one-dimensional (1-D) simulation based on the conservation equation of the first law of thermodynamics as e.g. in [33–37], and as detailed in section 4.2. This modelling requires strong assumptions but provides results in the right order of magnitude with low computational complexity. The second type, much more frequently used in literature, is by the Finite Volume Method (FVM) as for example in [38–42] and detailed in section 4.3. This approach, if the discretization procedures are applied properly, is expected to give more precise results and is more flexible (for example by considering much better the geometrical parameters) but it has the disadvantage of being complex and much more demanding in terms of computing time and power. Both the 1-D and FVM modelling are based on the fluid mechanics equations, which means that the flow should stay in the continuum flow regime and not achieve the rarefied regime. To validate this assumption, the Knudsen Number (Kn) can be used. It is a dimensionless number defined as the ratio of the molecular mean free path length λ to a representative physical length scale L_c :

$$Kn = \frac{\lambda}{L_c} \quad 4.1-1$$

To compute the Knudsen number in our case, we use the mixing chamber diameter as characteristic length L_c and the molecular mean free path length λ is taken from the literature [43]. To ensure that the pump is working on continuum flow, the Knudsen number should stay below 10^{-2} [44, 45].

4.1.1 1-D modelling

The basics of 1-D modelling introduced by Keenan et al.

Keenan et al. introduced in [33] a one-dimensional ejector modelling method in 1950 under the sponsorship of the Elliott Company and then has taken part to a program at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology under the sponsorship of the Navy Department, Bureau of Ordnance Contract Nord 9661. The method they present is based on the assumptions of perfect and isentropic fluid. Being a pioneer, it is limited to the specific framework of pure air ejectors. They obtains very good results in this case. However, a number of their mixing equations are based on ASME formulae and therefore incorporate many experimental data. It is interesting to note that they discuss the mixing conditions of the fluids in detail and caution about the limited validity of their models.

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1-D simulation by Huang et al.

Based on Keenan's et al. article [33], Huang et al. [34] rework and simplify Keenan's model so that it no longer refers to ASME equations. They use the same assumptions as those introduced by Keenan, i.e. those of a perfect isentropic fluid. They introduce 4 efficiency parameters and based on experiments, give experimental values of these efficiencies as a function of the fluid and the diameter ratio τ . They always work in a pure case but extend to other fluids such as steam or the refrigerant R141b.

Amelioration and first mixture modelling by He et al.

He et al. further develop the 1-D model by taking into account the entropy variation [35]. However, this requires a very detailed knowledge of the fluid used. They also address the case of modelling the mixture but only in the two-phase case (presence of the liquid and gas phase of the same fluid) but not in the case of two different fluids. Moreover, this modelling is mainly based on experimental data. They also present numerous experimental cases involving many fluids.

The Kumar and Ooi modelling

Kumar and Ooi present in [36] a more theoretical and less experimental model of an ejector based on the He et al. article [35]. They greatly simplify the equations used by He et al. and focus more specifically on Fanno flows. Fanno flow is adiabatic flow in a duct of constant area where the effect of friction is taken into account. It is noted that the equations they arrive at are very similar to those of Keenan et al. and Huang et al. [33]. Their case is however reduced the case of using R141b as the primary and secondary fluid.

Li et al. model extension

Based on the previous work, Li et al. present an algorithm to calculate the performance of the ejector not only in the critical case but also in the subcritical case. However, they model it only in a linear way. This allows the backing pressure to be calculated [37]. They also study in depth the efficiency parameters as introduced by Huang et al. for new fluids [33]. However, they are limited to the case where the primary and secondary fluids are the same.

Conclusion of the state-of-the-art for 1-D modelling

Thus, while there are several high-performance 1-D models, they are all mono-fluidic. Indeed, studying ejectors in the thermal context (especially for heat pumps), the models developed are very well adapted to this need, based largely on a perfect and thorough knowledge of the fluid used, which is not our case. An extension of these models based on stronger assumptions but requiring less knowledge of the fluid will be more suitable in our case. Furthermore, it will be necessary to extend our model to the specific case where the primary and secondary fluids are not the same.

4.1.2 FVM modelling

There is a very large amount of data on FVM simulation of ejector pumps. We will therefore present here only three very complete articles that are perfectly representative of the literature on the FVM simulation of ejectors.

Sriveerakul et al.

Sriveerakul et al. present a paper in two parts on pure steam ejectors [38, 39]. They compare FVM simulations they have performed with the corresponding experiments also performed by them. Their experimental protocol has a huge positive point, which is that they are able to take a pressure reading at several points of the ejector as shown in Fig. 12. Thus, a local comparison of the values is possible and one is much more precise on the analysis of possible deviations. Thus, it can be noticed that the largest areas of difference appear in the mixing chamber. Moreover, their simulation also extends to subcritical mode.

Fig. 12: Test bench with multiple pressure points. Taken from [38].

Croquer et al.

Croquer et al. published a two-part article simulating the case of a single-fluid ejector operating on R134a [40, 41]. This article presents a complete and detailed study of the solvers used and their influence on the results. They also study in an exhaustive way some hypotheses such as the ideal gas and several options of solvers frequently used (as we will detail in section 4.3).

Sicuro et al.

Sicuro et al. have published an article presenting an FVM model of an air ejector in the aeronautical context [42]. They have studied in depth the different solvers and the influence of these on the results. They also took a special interest in the throttling of the secondary fluid (as defined in section 4.2), which is a key point of this study. Then, they performed a sensitivity study and an optimization of the ejector geometry.

Conclusion of the state-of-the-art for FVM modelling

There are plenty of sources that perform FVM simulations. These allow enormous flexibility since, in addition to being able to take into account the entire geometry and weaker thermodynamic assumptions; they extend perfectly to both the critical and sub-critical regime. Moreover, these simulations allow highlighting complex phenomena such as the throttling of the secondary fluid or the type of shock wave that appears in the diffuser. They also allow a geometrical optimisation of the pump. However, this type of simulation has a significant disadvantage in terms of time and complexity of the calculations. If the FVM modelling is a tool that will be of great help to refine our results, it

remains very expensive and it seems unreasonable to carry out the whole of our work based only on this modelling.

4.1.3 Our modelling approach

We can therefore note that despite a rich literature, there is no source that explicitly deals with cases where the primary and secondary fluids are very different. For modelling mercury ejector pumps we take the following two-stage approach: first, we start by implementing a one-dimensional model based on the Li et al. article [37] which we will adapt to the case of fluid mixtures with very light secondary fluids (cf. section 4.2). That will allow us to produce a rough pre-design with minimal computational effort. This pre-design will subsequently be optimized using detailed FVM simulations in mixture case (cf. section 4.3) to produce the final design.

4.2 1-D modelling approach

4.2.1 Description of the initial model

The initial 1-D model is mainly based on literature [36, 37, 46], reflecting the standard operation cases of ejector pumps in industry. While these models are based on fundamental thermodynamic relations, they are using several efficiency parameters to fit to experimental data. However, because there is currently a lack of such data for mercury ejector pumps, our model does not initially rely on any efficiency factor. The models in the literature are in close agreement. In order to better understand the notations used, the notations are explained in Fig. 11 and Fig. 13.

Fig. 13: Graphic representations of the variables involved in the 1-D model. The colours represent the different fluids; the arrows represent the speed of the fluid.

The initial 1-D model is using the following hypotheses:

- 1- The working fluid is an ideal gas with constant heat capacity c_p and heat capacity ratio γ
- 2- The flow inside the ejector is one dimensional, steady and isentropic with the exception of shock waves

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- 3- The ejector walls are adiabatic
- 4- The kinetic energy of primary and secondary fluids at their respective inlets and of the mixed fluid at the outlet are negligible
- 5- Prior to the cross-section y - y where the secondary flow is choking, the primary flow stimulates but does not mix (thermodynamic moving wall) with the secondary flow. The two streams then begin to mix at a constant pressure ($P_m = P_{py} = P_{sy}$) (see Fig. 13).

The following presents the equations for the different regions along the ejector, i.e. in the mixing section, the mixing chamber, and the diffuser.

Primary flow to mixing section y - y

First of all, the primary mass flow rate \dot{m}_p can be easily expressed as a function of boundary and geometric conditions as it chokes in the primary nozzle throat [47]:

$$\dot{m}_p = \frac{P_{p0} A_t}{\sqrt{T_{p0}}} \sqrt{\frac{\gamma}{R^*} \left(\frac{2}{\gamma+1}\right)^{\frac{\gamma+1}{\gamma-1}}}, \quad 4.2-1$$

where P_{p0} denotes the primary inlet pressure, A_t the primary nozzle throat area, T_{p0} the primary inlet temperature, gamma the ratio of the specific heats and R^* the specific gas constant.

With the isentropic approximation, and knowing that the primary fluid is choking at the nozzle, the following equations apply:

$$\frac{P_{p0}}{P_{py}} = \left[1 + Ma_{py}^2 \frac{(\gamma - 1)}{2}\right]^{\frac{\gamma}{\gamma-1}} \quad 4.2-2$$

$$\frac{A_{py}}{A_t} = \frac{Ma_t}{Ma_{py}} \left[\frac{2 + Ma_{py}^2 (\gamma - 1)}{1 + \gamma}\right]^{\frac{\gamma+1}{2(\gamma-1)}} \quad 4.2-3$$

With P_{py} the primary fluid pressure at section y , A_{py} the area of the primary flow at section y , Ma_t the Mach number at the primary throat and Ma_{py} the Mach number of the primary fluid at section y .

As the flow is sonic in the primary nozzle throat, $Ma_t = 1$ applies.

Secondary flow to mixing section y - y

The pressure at section y is given on one hand by the fifth hypothesis and on the other hand by the isentropic approximation [47]:

$$P_{py} = P_{sy} = P_{s0} \left[1 + Ma_{sy}^2 \frac{\gamma - 1}{2}\right]^{\frac{\gamma}{1-\gamma}} \quad 4.2-4$$

Where P_{sy} denotes the secondary fluid pressure at section y , P_{s0} the secondary fluid inlet pressure, Ma_{sy} the Mach number of the secondary fluid at section y .

Due to the fifth assumption, we can compute the area of the secondary fluid at the y section A_{sy} knowing the mixing chamber area A_m as shown in Fig. 13:

$$A_{sy} = A_m - A_{py} \quad 4.2-5$$

With the fifth hypothesis (secondary fluid is choking) and knowing the secondary inlet temperature T_{s0} , we can compute the secondary mass flow rate \dot{m}_s at section y [47]:

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$$\dot{m}_s = \frac{P_{s0} A_{sy}}{\sqrt{T_{s0}}} \sqrt{\frac{\gamma}{R^*} \left(\frac{2}{\gamma + 1} \right)^{\frac{\gamma+1}{\gamma-1}}} \quad 4.2-6$$

The entrainment ratio follows from equation 3.1-2.

Mixing chamber

With the equation of the momentum conservation, we can compute the velocity of the mixed fluid v_m as function of the the speed of the primary fluid at y -section v_{py} and the speed of secondary fluid at y section v_{sy} :

$$v_m(\dot{m}_s + \dot{m}_p) = \dot{m}_p v_{py} + \dot{m}_s v_{sy} \quad 4.2-7$$

And then use the energy conservation to compute the temperature of the mixture:

$$\dot{m}_p \left(c_p T_{py} + \frac{v_{py}^2}{2} \right) + \dot{m}_s \left(c_p T_{sy} + \frac{v_{sy}^2}{2} \right) = (\dot{m}_s + \dot{m}_p) \left(c_p T_m + \frac{v_m^2}{2} \right) \quad 4.2-8$$

We can then compute the Mach number of the mixture Ma_m .

Diffuser

At the critical point, the mixed flow undergoes a shock process with a sharp pressure rise (from the mixing pressure P_m to the diffuser pressure P_d) and a fall of the Mach number to the diffuser Mach number Ma_d , which can be approximated by the normal shock equations [47]:

$$\frac{P_d}{P_m} = 1 + \frac{2\gamma}{\gamma + 1} (Ma_m^2 - 1) \quad 4.2-9$$

$$Ma_d^2 = \frac{2 + (\gamma - 1) Ma_m^2}{2\gamma Ma_m^2 - (\gamma - 1)} \quad 4.2-10$$

Assuming then an isentropic process to achieve the fourth hypothesis: $v_{out}=0$, we can compute the output pressure P_{cc} :

$$\frac{P_{cc}}{P_d} = \left[1 + Ma_d^2 \frac{\gamma - 1}{2} \right]^{\frac{\gamma}{1-\gamma}} \quad 4.2-11$$

To compute the critical backing pressure P_{cb} pressure, we only use the same equations as for P_{cc} but by assuming at 4.2-8 that $\dot{m}_s = 0$. In this case, $T_{py}=T_m$ and $v_{py}=v_m$ so $Ma_m=Ma_{py}$. Then the equations 4.2-10 and 4.2-11 allow us to obtain the values to calculate the pressure P_{cb} with the following equation:

$$\frac{P_{cb}}{P_d} = \left[1 + Ma_d^2 \frac{\gamma - 1}{2} \right]^{\frac{\gamma}{1-\gamma}} \quad 4.2-12$$

4.2.2 Development of an improved 1-D model

As discussed in [48], the fifth hypothesis that is assuming that the secondary fluid is choking is questionable (see [42]). Indeed, Fig. 14 shows for the limit case how two different solvers both perfectly fitting the experimental data converge for one solver to a secondary fluid choking solution and for another one to a secondary fluid non-chocking solution.

Fig. 14: Simulation of the case [48] with two different turbulence models. Adapted from [42].

Pushing the reasoning to the case of pumps, where the primary fluid is different from the secondary fluid and especially to the cases where their molar masses are very different, the choking of the secondary fluid becomes physically impossible. Indeed, in our relevant case where the primary fluid is mercury and pumping fluids with much lower molar masses such as helium or hydrogen, and assuming that the total energy from the primary fluid is given to the secondary one (which is a gross overestimation of reality) the maximum achievable mixing speed is about 500 m/s, and the mixing temperature about 200 K. Under these conditions, the primary mercury vapour is supersonic ($Ma \approx 4$), lighter secondary fluids like helium or hydrogen only reach $Ma \approx 0.6$ and $Ma \approx 0.4$ respectively (see equation 3.1-1). It can therefore be concluded that ejectors as foreseen for DEMO will always operate with subsonic secondary flow. Based on this observation, it is necessary to develop a more representative 1-D model in which the secondary fluid does not reach Mach 1 on the thermodynamic throat as presumed in the fifth assumption for the initial model above. Furthermore, the standard literature model assumes that primary and secondary fluid are identical (as typical in steam ejectors in industry), which is clearly not the case in the fusion context. That is why, the 1-D model is subsequently extended with a mixture model.

Iterative 1-D model

Theory

The idea of this new model is to compute the new mass flow rate without the hypothesis that the secondary fluid is choking at section y . However, we keep the used concept of the primary fluid creating a wall and the secondary fluid is thus caught in a thermodynamic nozzle (see Fig. 13). Without the hypothesis of choking, the mass flow rate computation of the secondary fluid is not the same (see 4.2-17). Using the isentropic relations (described in [47]) we can define the temperature and the density ρ ratios between the inlet and the y section:

$$\frac{T_{sy}}{T_0} = \left[\frac{2 + Ma_{sy}^2(\gamma - 1)}{2 + Ma_0^2(\gamma - 1)} \right] \quad 4.2-13$$

$$\frac{\rho_{sy}}{\rho_0} = \left[\frac{2 + Ma_{sy}^2(\gamma - 1)}{2 + Ma_0^2(\gamma - 1)} \right]^{\frac{\gamma}{1-\gamma}} \left[\frac{2 + Ma_{sy}^2(\gamma - 1)}{2 + Ma_0^2(\gamma - 1)} \right] \quad 4.2-14$$

$$= \left[1 + Ma_{sy}^2 \frac{\gamma - 1}{2} \right]^{\frac{1}{1-\gamma}} \quad 4.2-15$$

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Then we can compute the secondary mass flow rate:

$$\dot{m}_s = \rho_{sy} A_{sy} v_{sy} \quad 4.2-16$$

$$= \rho_{sy} A_{sy} \sqrt{\gamma R^* T_{sy}} Ma_{sy} \quad 4.2-17$$

Iteration algorithm and sensitivity of the results to the ΔP step

The algorithm of the necessary iteration procedure is depicted in [Fig. 15](#). When we create an iteration on the mass flow rate of the secondary fluid as a function of the pressure of point $P_{py}=P_{sy}$ (see algorithm in [Fig. 15](#)), we notice that the secondary mass flow rate reaches a maximum. It would seem, from the results obtained, that this maximum point is the operating point. Unfortunately, no rigorous mathematical demonstration has been produced for the moment and this is an unneglectable point of justification or even improvement of this model. Since we are moving from an analytic to an iterative calculation method, it is important to determine the order of magnitude that our ΔP increment step should have. We have therefore performed an increment convergence analysis. The results are given in [Fig. 16](#). In view of the very short calculation times, it seems prudent to guarantee a high reliability by keeping a safety margin on this parameter, which is why we will use an increment of 10^{-2} Pa in this study.

Fig. 15: Algorithm for the 1-D model

Fig. 16: Results of the increment variation on the secondary mass flow rate. Mercury vapour as primary fluid ($P_{p0}=500$ Pa, $T_{p0}=441.43$ K) and hydrogen as secondary fluid ($P_{s0}=10$ Pa, $T_{s0}=293.15$ K).

Benchmarking

A comparison of the initial 1-D model and the newly proposed iterative model results is plotted for the entrainment ratio in Fig. 17. The reference data to which the models are compared are taken from [34], which compiles numerous experimental and numerical data, varying both thermodynamic and geometrical parameters. The error between these two models and the experiment are shown in the box-and-whisker diagrams in Fig. 18. The complete data are available in Appendix 1 including the reference.

Fig. 17: Results of the entrainment ratio for the standard choking (orange) model and the newly proposed iterative one (blue). The experimental reference is from [34].

Fig. 18: Statistical repartition of the error between the iterative 1-D model and the experimental values (blue) and between the standard 1-D model and the experimental values (orange) (confer Fig. 17) represented in box-and-whisker diagrams.

It can be noticed that the trend of the experimental values is perfectly followed by the new model. Moreover, the analysis of the error shows us that despite a non-centred average error (represented by the cross in the diagram), the complete amplitude of the error (represented by the all line) is much smaller as compared with the previous literature model as it is the case for the lower and upper quartiles. Despite the fact that the boundary conditions (temperature and pressure) of the primary and secondary fluids were varied as well as the geometry (diameter of the primary nozzle), reservations are still to be kept in view of the type of data (all from the same experiment done with the same fluid) as well as the number of data in itself (39 values), which remains relatively low from a statistical point of view. Another remark that must be made is that there is no obvious correlation between the errors of the standard explicit model and of the one from the new iterative model.

4.2.3 Mixing law model

The literature 1-D model has to be adapted to work in case that primary and secondary fluid are not the same. By assuming the hypotheses of n perfect gases of molar isobaric heat capacity c_{P_i} and heat capacity ratio γ_i mixing in an isentropic way, we can demonstrate (complete demonstration available in Appendix 2) that the molar isobaric heat capacity \bar{c}_P and the heat capacity ratio $\bar{\gamma}$ of the mixture are:

$$\bar{c}_P = \left(\sum_i^n \frac{x_i}{R_i^*} \right)^{-1} + \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \frac{c_{P_i}}{\gamma_i} \quad 4.2-18$$

$$\bar{\gamma} = 1 + \frac{1}{\sum \sum \frac{x_i x_j}{\gamma_i - 1} \frac{M_j}{M_i}} \quad 4.2-19$$

with x_i the molar fraction of the species i , M_i the molar mass of the species i , $R_i^* = \frac{R}{M_i}$ the specific perfect gas constant of the species i and γ_i the heat capacity ratio of the species i .

Benchmarking the new iterative mixture 1-D model

Since there is no literature on multispecies ejector simulation, we have to compare to experimental data (the latter being also rare). In this context, the paper of Reddick et al. [49] is the only suitable reference with sufficient geometric references to be able to run a simulation and have a point of comparison. It presents parametric experiments for pumping CO₂ with a steam ejector. Based on [49] we can benchmark the improved 1-D-model for two experimental cases:

- 1- Primary fluid: steam, secondary fluid: steam (i.e. single species case)
- 2- Primary fluid: steam, secondary fluid: steam + CO₂ mixture

The experiments covered 4 nozzle diameters, different CO₂ mass fractions, and varied inlet pressure. The results of the entrainment ratio agreement with the experiment are shown on [Fig. 19](#). The complete curves are available in Appendix 3. We can see that the results for the entrainment ratio are in very good agreement with the experimental measurements. This also verifies that the newly developed mixture model works correctly in the edge case of similar species. The values of the critical pressures are less accurate but the pump should work at the plateau point so it will not be a huge problem for us but remain a point of future improvement of this 1-D model.

Fig. 19: Results of the entrainment ratio computed with the iterative model for the pure steam (blue) and a mixing of steam and CO₂ (orange). The experimental reference comes from [49].

4.2.4 Conclusion and discussion and limitation of the 1-D model

In view of the results obtained we can conclude that the new improved one-dimensional model works correctly. A possible evolution of this model would be to justify in a more rigorous way the choice of the operating point in the case where the second fluid does not choke. Furthermore, a new model where we would take into account a progressive mixing between the primary and secondary fluid could be much more accurate but it would also be much more complex to implement [50, 51].

For our problem, the developed model is felt to be sufficient to give an initial indication, which we will refine subsequently by detailed simulations using the finite volume method, as is described in the next section.

Since it is assumed that the velocity of the secondary fluid is constant at the thermodynamic throat created by the primary fluid and the mixing chamber (by definition of 1-D modelling) and that the surface area of the mixing chamber is calculated by subtracting the surface area of the mixing chamber from the surface area of the primary flow (see equation 4.2-5), it follows that the diameter of the mixing chamber is not an output data but an input data. Indeed, by increasing the diameter of the mixing chamber without changing the diameter of the primary nozzle throat (which allows to calculate the surface of the thermodynamic throat), it is possible to increase the secondary mass flow arbitrarily, which represents a flagrant violation of the energy conservation. In order to avoid this deviation, it was decided to always take a diameter of the mixing chamber proportional to the diameter of the primary nozzle. In order to determine the value of this coefficient, a study of the literature was performed and is shown in Fig. 20. In view of the results, it was decided to use a diameter ratio (defined as mixing chamber diameter over nozzle throat diameter) of $\tau=3.7$.

Fig. 20: Evaluation of the diameter ratio in view of the values in the literature. All detailed values and references are given in Appendix 4.

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4.3 FVM modelling approach

Concept of FVM method

In the case of complex systems, it is possible to solve the equations of fluid mechanics numerically. This field is called Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD). The finite volume method (FVM) is a branch of the CFD. It is a method for generating and solving partial differential equations numerically by turning it into discrete algebraic equations over differential finite volumes. The FVM is regarded as a strictly conservative approximation since the flux entering and exiting the volumes are equal. The FVM is advantageous in CFD because of its conservatism and the straightforward, non-intrusive implementation of the boundary conditions. In our case, we will use the ANSYS Fluent® software.

The Navier-Stokes equations

The Navier-Stokes equations represent the equations of the three great principles of physical conservation which are the conservation of mass, the conservation of momentum (Newton's second law) and the conservation of energy. Using the Eulerian notation (the one adapted to the FVM), the Navier-Stokes equation system reads:

Continuity equation (conservation of mass) [52, 53]:

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \vec{\nabla} \cdot (\rho \vec{V}) = 0 \quad 4.3-1$$

Momentum conservation equation [52, 53]:

$$\frac{\partial (\rho \vec{V})}{\partial t} + \vec{\nabla} \cdot (\rho \vec{V} \vec{V}) = -\vec{\nabla} P + \vec{\nabla} \Sigma + \rho \vec{g} + \vec{f} \quad 4.3-2$$

Energy conservation equation [52, 53]:

$$\frac{\partial (\rho E)}{\partial t} + \vec{\nabla} \cdot (\rho E \vec{V}) = -\vec{\nabla} \cdot (P \vec{V}) + \vec{\nabla} \cdot (\Sigma \vec{V}) - \vec{\nabla} \cdot (\kappa \nabla T) + \rho \vec{g} \cdot \vec{V} + \vec{q} \quad 4.3-3$$

In these equations,

- t represent the time
- ρ is the volume mass of the fluid
- \vec{V} is the Eulerian speed of the fluid
- P is the pressure tensor
- Σ is the viscous stress tensor
- κ is the thermal conductivity
- T is the temperature
- \vec{g} is gravity acceleration constant
- E is the total mass energy
- \vec{f} External forces
- \vec{q} External sources and sinks of energy

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Turbulence modelling

There are many different ways to simulate turbulences from the Navier-Stokes equations. In order to save a lot of time and power computation and considering that we are working on steady state, we concentrate on the Reynold Average Navier-Stokes equations (RANS equations). These equations are the time averaged version of the fluid motion equations and makes it possible to describe the intrinsically unstable turbulent flow in an averaged steady state [54]. In agreement with the literature [24, 27–32], it has been determined that the two most suitable systems of equations are the k- ϵ realizable model and k- ω SST model [55]. In order to improve the speed of calculation, the models presented can neglect certain parts of the equations. These can then be taken into consideration as an option at the user's discretion. In the following section, we will focus on 5 different options:

1- Production Kato Launder

The Kato-Launder modification is an ad-hoc modification of the turbulent production term in the k equation. The main purpose of the modification is to reduce the tendency that many two-equation models have to over-predict the turbulent production in regions with large normal strain, i.e. regions with strong acceleration or deceleration [56].

2- Viscous heating

Viscous heating represents the effect of an irreversible process by means of which the work done by a fluid on adjacent layers due to the action of shear forces is transformed into heat [57].

3- Low Reynolds corrections

In contrast with the high Reynolds number turbulence models, there is no need of the wall functions to bridge between the core and the near wall regions in the low Reynolds corrections k- ϵ models. The low Reynolds corrections models use damping functions instead to account for the near wall effects. The damping functions [55] bring about the opportunity of modelling of a broader range of the flow fields [58]. The limitations imposed by the wall functions are described by Wilcox [59].

4- Compressibility effects

For high-Mach-number flows, compressibility affects turbulence through so-called "dilatation dissipation", which is normally neglected in the modelling of incompressible flows [59]. Neglecting the dilatation dissipation fails to predict the observed decrease in spreading rate with increasing Mach number for compressible mixing and other free shear layers. To account for these effects in the k- ϵ models in ANSYS Fluent®, a dilatation dissipation term is included in the k equation [55]. This term is modelled according to a proposal by Sarkar [60].

5- Production limiter

A disadvantage of standard two-equation turbulence models is the excessive generation of the turbulence energy in the vicinity of stagnation points. In order to avoid the build-up of turbulent kinetic energy in the stagnation regions, the production term in the turbulence equations can be limited [55].

k- ω SST model

The different options of the $k-\omega$ SST model have been studied on the case of [39]. The results are listed in [Tab. 1](#). It seems that for our case, the options of viscous heating, compressibility effects and Kato Launder production should be retained.

Tab. 1: Options study on the $k-\omega$ SST model based on the entrainment ratio. References comes from [39].

case studied	Production Kato Launder	Viscous heating	Low Reynolds corrections	Compressibility effects	Error
1	no	yes	no	no	30.73%
1	yes	no	no	yes	18.30%
1	no	no	no	yes	18.29%
1	no	no	no	no	18.29%
1	no	no	yes	no	34.08%
1	yes	yes	no	yes	12.50%
2	yes	yes	no	yes	3.15%
3	yes	yes	no	yes	13.68%

$$*error = \frac{|\text{secondary mass flow rate for without options} - \text{secondary mass flow rate for with options}|}{|\text{secondary mass flow rate for without options}|}$$

k- ϵ realizable model

The different options of the $k-\epsilon$ realizable model have been studied on the case of [39]. The results are shown in the [Tab. 2](#). It seems that the case with the options of viscous heating, compressibility effects and limiter production should be retained.

Tab. 2: Options study on the $k-\epsilon$ realizable model based on the entrainment ratio. References comes from [39].

Case studied	Viscous heating	Compressibility effects	Production limiter	Error
2	no	no	no	16.17%
2	no	no	yes	26.29%
2	no	yes	no	3.27%
2	no	yes	yes	5.65%
2	yes	no	no	14.12%
2	yes	no	yes	12.58%
2	yes	yes	no	3.55%
2	yes	yes	yes	3.33%

$$*error = \frac{|\text{secondary mass flow rate for without options} - \text{secondary mass flow rate for with options}|}{|\text{secondary mass flow rate for without options}|}$$

Based on the literature survey and the study regarding the solver options summarized above we can conclude that the choice of the turbulence model and its options has a relatively small influence on the final solution. As we found that the $k-\omega$ SST model is converging a bit faster than the $k-\epsilon$ realizable model, we chose the $k-\omega$ SST model for all simulations in the present work.

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Thermo-physical properties

Equation of state

If the velocity, pressure and temperature are calculated from the conservation equations above, the system is still missing equations to make it complete. In particular, an equation of state is missing. In the literature, the compressible ideal gas law is commonly used [38–42, 61, 62] in order to compute the density. This is also the case for our FVM model:

$$\rho = \frac{MP}{RT} \quad 4.3-4$$

In some applications in literature, the applicability of the ideal gas law is questionable. One simplest way to check the validity of the ideal gas law is to check the compressibility ratio z defined as

$$z = \frac{PV}{nRT} \quad 4.3-5$$

with P the pressure, V the volume, n the mole number, R the ideal gas constant, T the temperature and M the molar mass. Thus, the compressibility ratio gives the deviation of the ideal gas law.

The article from Croquer et al. [40] studies the influence of such an assumption on the performances of an ejector pump. They use R134a as working fluid at 3188 kPa and 89.13°C. By comparing it to the Redlich-Kwong-Soave equation of state and to an experimental database, they show a constant difference in the entrainment ratio of 12% and an unnoticeable difference on the Mach number and on the pressure. At this pressure and temperature, the compressibility ratio for R134a is smaller than 0.55 [63]. We will show later that we are always well above this value, thus justifying the use of this equation.

Transport properties

Thus, this equation system is complete but is dependent on fluid transport properties such as viscosity, thermal conductivity and mass diffusion coefficients. While the values of the latter are available in the ANSYS Fluent® database for very well-known fluids such as steam, they are not available for fluids such as mercury vapour or helium. In order to obtain a value for the latter, we use the kinetic theory based on Lennard-Jones potentials (experimentally determined) and degrees of freedom of the specie. Thus, the molar specific heat capacity c_p is computed as function of the degrees of freedom f and of the molar mass M as depicted in equation 4.3-9 [55].

$$c_p = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{R}{M} (f + 2) \quad 4.3-6$$

To compute the diffusion coefficient, Fluent uses a modified form of the Chapman-Enskog formula (detailed in [64]) [55]. For the viscosity μ , ANSYS Fluent® uses the equation 4.3-7 [55] dependant on the characteristic length σ and the energy parameter ϵ/k_B . The Ω_μ is the double integral molecular distribution function as defined by Chapman-Enskog [64].

$$\mu = 2.67 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{MT}}{\sigma^2 \Omega_\mu \left(\frac{T}{\epsilon/k_B} \right)} \quad 4.3-7$$

Then, to compute the thermal conductivity κ , ANSYS Fluent® uses the following equation [55]:

$$\kappa = \frac{15}{4} \cdot \frac{R}{M} \mu \left[\frac{4}{15} \frac{c_p M}{R} + \frac{1}{3} \right] \quad 4.3-8$$

In order to verify the hypothesis made on the basis of kinetic theory, it was decided to compare with experimental data from the literature. Indeed, the article by Vukalovich et al. [65] is a proven reference and corroborated by other independent studies as [66–68] on mercury vapour data. The comparison was carried out on the μ dynamic viscosity. The results presented in Fig. 21 show a very strong corroboration between the value of the dynamic viscosity obtained during our simulation with ANSYS Fluent® and the results provided by the literature. We can thus validate the use of kinetic theory.

Fig. 21: Results of the dynamic viscosity μ with the kinetic theory compared to the empirical values from [65].

4.3.1 Description of the model implementation

Axisymmetric and boundary conditions

In order to simplify the computations, we compare the pressure ratio as defined in equation 4.3-9 in axisymmetric 2D model and 3D model. The pressure ratio χ characterises the compression achieved (pressure change between secondary fluid suction and discharge pressure) in relation to the maximum compression ever achieved (pressure between primary and secondary fluid). It should not be confused with the compression ratio Ψ as defined by equation 4.3-10. The latter is the ratio of critical backing pressure on secondary inlet pressure.

The Fig. 22 shows that the difference between 3D and axisymmetric 2D cases are very small. In consequence and inspecting the geometry of an ejector pump, we assume that the simulation can be reduced to a two-dimensional axisymmetric simulation. We can then apply the following boundary conditions: Primary total pressure and temperature at the primary inlet, total secondary pressure and

temperature at the secondary inlet and total backing pressure at the outlet. The wall is considered as perfectly adiabatic with a no-slip condition.

$$\chi = \frac{P_c - P_{s0}}{P_{P0} - P_{s0}} \quad 4.3-9$$

$$\psi = \frac{P_{cc}}{P_{s0}} \quad 4.3-10$$

Fig. 22: Results of the pressure ratio χ as unction of the entrainment ratio for 2-D and 3-D FVM simulations. The experimental data comes from [69].

Choice of the mesh

It was decided to have a minimum of 20 elements in the nozzle throat diameter (equivalent to the smallest dimension). In order to ensure a good overall quality of the mesh, we also used three indicators:

1- The aspect ratio

The aspect ratio is a measure of the stretching of a cell. It is computed as the ratio of the maximum value to the minimum value of any of the following distances: the distances between the cell centroid and face centroids, and the distances between the cell centroid and nodes (see Fig. 23). Based on the software recommendations, we use a maximum aspect ratio of 18 [55].

Fig. 23: Definition of the aspect ratio for 2D quadrilateral element.

2- The orthogonality

Orthogonality is a measure of the quality of a mesh, and is calculated as shown on [Fig. 24](#) from the dot products of each vector \vec{r}_{f_i} pointing from the centroid of a cell toward the center of each of its faces, and the corresponding face area vector \vec{A}_i as

$$\text{orthogonality} = \min_i \left[\frac{\vec{A}_i \cdot \vec{r}_{f_i}}{|\vec{A}_i| |\vec{r}_{f_i}|} \right] \quad 4.3-11$$

Based on the software recommendations, we use a minimum orthogonality above 0.1 [55].

3- The skewness

The skewness is a non-dimensional parameter calculated using the normalized angle deviation method (see [Fig. 25](#)), and is defined by

$$\text{skewness} = \max \left[\frac{q_{\max} - q_e}{180 - q_e}, \frac{q_e - q_{\min}}{q_e} \right] \quad 4.3-12$$

where q_{\max} is the largest angle in the face or cell, q_{\min} is the smallest angle in the face or cell and q_e is the angle for an equiangular face or cell (e.g., 60° for a triangle and 90° for a square). Based on the software recommendations, we use a maximum skewness below 0.95 with an average value less than 0.33 [55].

[Fig. 24](#): Definition of the orthogonality for 2D quadrilateral element.

[Fig. 25](#): Definition of the skewness for 2D quadrilateral element.

In order to prevent problems in the walls, a gradual refinement of the walls was carried out (see [Fig. 26](#)). To ensure the validity of such a method, a mesh sensitivity study was performed (see [Tab. 3](#)). An element size of 0.25 mm corresponds to 9 elements in the nozzle throat radius and 0.2mm correspond to 11 elements. We can see that a huge variation of the number of integration points (points where the different variables of the simulation are computed) by factor of 1.8 obtained by increasing the number of element and by a factor of 4 obtain by increasing the order of each element (see [Fig. 27](#)) doesn't change significantly the global results. Indeed, the variation of the secondary mass flow rate between the coarsest and finest mesh sizes is well below 1%. Thus, we can be confident on the mesh quality.

Fig. 26: Typical mesh pattern.

Fig. 27: 2D quadrilateral mesh parameter. Linear element on right (with one integration point) and quadratic element on the left (with four integration points).

Tab. 3: Results of the mesh convergence

element type	element size [mm]	mesh nodes	mesh elements	sec. mass flow [kg s ⁻¹]	sec. error*	Throughput [Pa m ³ s ⁻¹]	Throughput [Torr L s ⁻¹]
linear	0.25	133102	130792	1.77E-04	8.37E-03	15.2676115	114.507086
linear	0.2	248189	245192	1.76E-04	5.69E-07	15.1408825	113.556619
quadratic	0.2	248189	245192	1.76E-04	0	15.1408739	113.556554

element type	element size [mm]	mesh nodes	mesh elements	Primary mass flow [kg s ⁻¹]	primary error*	outlet mass flow rate [kg s ⁻¹]	outlet error*	mass conservation [kg s ⁻¹]
linear	0.25	133102	130792	0.0042812	2.34E-06	-0.004458	3.31E-04	2.00E-10
linear	0.2	248189	245192	0.0042812	0.00	-0.004457	1.35E-06	-1.24E-08
quadratic	0.2	248189	245192	0.0042812	0.00	-0.004457	0.00	-6.50E-09

$$*error = \frac{|value \text{ for quadratic } 0.2\text{mm element} - value \text{ for the simulated case}|}{|value \text{ for quadratic } 0.2\text{mm element}|}$$

4.3.2 Benchmarking of the FVM ejector model

Pure case

To validate the correct implementation of our FVM model, we have compared it to results from literature, including experimental and simulation results. For validation purposes the article of Sriveerakul et al. [39] is a good choice, as it presents local results for the static pressure along the ejector axis which gives us the opportunity for a very precise comparison (not only integral quantities like the entrainment ratio). The results plotted in [Fig. 28](#) show that our FVM model produces results very close to their FVM simulation and experimental measurements. The integral averaged error with the literature simulations is 41%, and with the literature experiments is 21%.

Fig. 28: Results of the static pressure computed along the ejector wall for CFD and as measured experimentally. Experimental data and complementary simulation from [39].

Mixing case

Since there is no literature on multispecies ejector simulation, we have to compare to experimental data (the latter being also rare). In this context, the paper of Reddick et al. [49] is the only suitable reference which presents parametric experiments for pumping CO_2 with a steam ejector. Thus, a comparison between their results for different CO_2 rates in a steam ejector and our FVM model are shown in [Fig. 29](#). The deviations are at average about 30% related to the experimental results, rather independent of the increase of the mass fraction of CO_2 . One may therefore also speculate that the paper suffers from unaccounted systematic experimental errors which may be due to the temperature and pressure measurement being relatively far away from the ejector and the presence of elbows between this measurement point and the ejector.

Fig. 29: Results of the entrainment ratio for different CO₂ mass fractions in a steam ejector computed with CFD (orange) and compared with literature experimental data (blue) [49].

In summary, on the basis of the limited literature data available we conclude that our FVM simulations give reasonable results. We therefore consider the FVM simulation methodology as verified.

4.4 Validation and application for mercury vapour ejector pumps

Power and Dennis have published an article about what they titled an “Unusual mercury ejector pump” [70]. This article published in 1960 is the only one we found on a mercury ejector pump. It presents a serial 3 stage mercury vapour ejector pump (see Fig. 30) driven by a primary mercury vapour pressure around 400 Torr (53 330 Pa). The global pump has a throughput of 20 L Torr s⁻¹ (2.6 m³ Pa s⁻¹) at 1 Torr (133 Pa) against a backing pressure of 100 Torr (13 300 Pa). They also tested each stage separately and give a curve of the throughput as a function of the inlet pressure for each stage. Between each stage, the mercury vapour is condensed. This article will be our reference for a final validation of our models. We will concentrate on the secondary stage which is working in both critical and subcritical modes. Even if it is not explicitly given in the article, we have deduced from the article the geometrical properties of the second stage given in Tab. 4.

Tab. 4: List of the geometrical properties (all in mm) [59].

Nozzle throat diameter	2.27
NXP	53
Mixing chamber diameter	11
Mixing chamber length	52
Diffuser length	134
Diffuser output diameter	37

Fig. 30: Design taken from [16] (left) and photograph (right) taken from [70] of the Power and Dennis mercury pump [70].

4.4.1 1-D simulation

By using the iterative 1-D model with mixture law, as detailed in section 4.2, iterated on the goal throughput, we compute the achievable inlet pressure. We can compare the results between the experiment conducted in [70] and our model. These results are shown in Fig. 31. First of all, we can see that the curves, although different, are in the same order of magnitude. There are many possible reasons for the differences between the curves and it is difficult to clearly identify the ins and outs of each of these causes. However, one of the most important is the lack of geometric data in the article, which had to be extrapolated from the figures. We can also note that the adiabatic wall assumption of the 1-D model is wrong in this case. Indeed, the walls are metallic, not insulated and even refrigerated by the cooled outlet flux (see section below), which invalidates the adiabatic wall hypothesis.

Fig. 31: Throughput as computed with the iterative model (orange) and as measured experimentally in reference [70].

4.4.2 FVM simulation

Thermo-physical properties

At the working temperature and pressure, the mercury compressibility ratio is greater than 0.9961 [68]. Therefore, the ideal gas law (see section 4.3) is assumed as the equation of state. Because the temperature dependent transport properties of especially mercury vapor are not available in literature we make use of the ANSYS Fluent® functionality to calculate them from kinetic theory expressions [55]. For consistency we use the same approach for the secondary fluid (air and helium). In order to calculate the transport properties from kinetic theory an intermolecular potential is required. In ANSYS Fluent® only the Lennard-Jones potential is supported [55]. For each species the characteristic length σ and the energy parameter ϵ/k_B have to be provided. For the species considered in the present work these parameters were taken from [71] and are tabulated in Tab. 5. The mixture properties are calculated from the contributing species based on the mixture laws explained in [55].

Tab. 5: Lennard-Jones parameters for all species considered in the present work. Values taken from [71].

	ϵ/k_B [K]	σ [Å]
Mercury	851	2.898
Air	84	3.689
Helium	10.22	2.556

Hypothesis on isobaric condensation

To verify that the backing pressure of the experiment which is measured further in the outlet pipe and especially after the mercury condensation is the same as the outlet pressure of our simulation, we have done a simulation of the entire pump including mercury condensation. Similar to the experimental setup this is implemented by adding an annular gap linking the outlet of the ejector mixing chamber to the pump outlet. The walls of this gap are cooled in the experimental stages to condense the mercury vapour as shown on [Fig. 32](#). In the simulation setup we implement an isothermal boundary condition on the walls of the gap at 293.15K. Condensation of mercury is simulated in a simplistic way by implementing a chemical reaction on the wall that removes mercury from the simulation domain. The results obtained are shown in [Fig. 33](#) and [Fig. 34](#).

It can be seen that the static mixture pressure stays approximatively constant in the reservoir downstream of the ejector and along the annular gap where the mercury vapour is condensed. Therefore, and in order not to make the FVM model unnecessarily complex, the simulations in the following are limited to include only the ejector geometry, excluding the annular gap.

Fig. 32: Mercury ejector with condensation part of the primary fluid. Adapted from [70].

Fig. 33: Molar fraction of air for the ejector pump with the mercury condensation.

Fig. 34: Static pressure limited at $4 \cdot 10^3$ Pa for the ejector pump with the mercury condensation.

Article ejector pump simulation

The results of the FVM simulations of the article are plotted in [Fig. 35](#).

Fig. 35: Results of the throughput against inlet pressure computed with the FVM method for two different inlet pressures and of the experimental reference [70].

First of all, we must keep in mind that we can only compare against this one single literature reference, where we measured the dimensions from a small plot. This unavoidably brings additional inaccuracies so that a critical position must be maintained regarding the conclusions of this comparison. Taking this into account, the results obtained are relatively satisfactory. Let us note that surprisingly the ultimate pressure achievable is lower in the experiments reported in the article than predicted by the simulations. However, the order of magnitude of this pressure is in good quantitative agreement with the values of the article. Regarding the flow rate, we notice that the one in the article is much lower than predicted by the simulations. This can be explained partly by the experimental process that could limit the flow (the size of the mercury liquefaction chamber, the outlet tube or other). Despite all these discrepancies, and given that we have no other data to compare with to improve, we conclude that the 1-D and FVM modelling give satisfactory results that can be used to, at least preliminarily, size an ejector pumping system operating with mercury as primary fluid.

5 DEMO ejector pump development

5.1 Summary of requirements

In order to guarantee a homogeneous vacuum, the tokamak is divided into 10 pumping sections, each of which representing $45 \text{ Pa m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ to be pumped. As defined in section 0, the requirement for this study is to bridge a pressure gap from 10 Pa to a pressure between 400 Pa and 7 000 Pa. As shown in Fig. 36, we separate the problem in two parts. The first stage of ejector pump will be directly integrated into the pumping ports after the LDPs in the tokamak building. For those ejectors the goal is to pump $9 \text{ Pa m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ per pumping port at an inlet pressure of approx. 10 Pa and against a backing pressure between 50 to 100 Pa. These ejectors should remain below 2 meters long to fit in the available space under the tokamak. For the second stage of ejectors, it will be organized in packs to fit in gloveboxes. A CAD drawing of a typical example of such a pack measuring $660 \times 548 \times 710 \text{ mm}$ can be found in Appendix 5. The target working pressure range of such an ejector pack is an inlet pressure of 50 Pa to 100 Pa and an outlet pressure of 400 Pa to 7 000 Pa. The total throughput to achieve is around $360 \text{ Pa m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ for the DIRT and $90 \text{ Pa m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ for the INTL. With this information, we can roughly determine the number of ejector pumps and their primary pressures. Then, a discussion could be held to determine whether it is preferable to use LRPs or ejector pumps and if the ejector pumps could be the solution to bridge the pressure gap between the LDPs and the LRPs. In order to have realistic results and taking into account the lack of literature on tritium or deuterium, helium was the gas species used for the dimensioning of this vacuum system.

Fig. 36: Global organisation of the DEMO pumping system including the ejectors (preliminary concept).

5.2 Sizing of the INTL first stage ejector pump

In view of the equations used, the assumptions made in the 1-D modelling, and the complexity of the FVM calculations, it is believed that the first compression stage is the most difficult to design, especially considering the size limitation (the length of these ejectors should not exceed 2 m as mentioned above). Indeed, as far as 1-D modelling is concerned, the assumptions of constant velocity, as a direct consequence of the one-dimensional aspect of the model, becomes less and less credible at low pressure. We are also limited in the number of possible compression stages (the best being to realize only one compression stage). In view of these constraints, and knowing that we work at low pressure (10 Pa as inlet pressure), a minimum size of mixing chamber diameter is given by a limit Knudsen number of 10^{-2} at a value of 175 mm. By upscaling the article pump [70], this diameter gives us an overall pump length of about 2m. According to Fig. 20, the primary nozzle throat diameter is then fixed to 50 mm.

1-D approach for the choice of the primary pressure

The aim is to pump $9 \text{ Pa m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ with a compression factor of at least 5 (in order to be in the pressure range above 50 Pa as define previously). Note that on the [Fig. 37](#) this minimum compression factor is guaranteed. The aim is then to maximise the compression factor while minimising the number of pumps (i.e. maximising the throughput). Thus, placing ourselves at the upper limit of $9 \text{ Pa m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ allows us to use only one ejector pump per tokamak section and to maximise the critical backing pressure. From the results of the 1-D simulation shown in [Fig. 37](#), it appears that a primary pressure of 1350 Pa is the maximum pressure one case use to guarantee a throughput of $9 \text{ Pa m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$. At this inlet pressure, the achievable backing pressure is around 160 Pa, which in the goal range (more than 3 times higher than the minimum required). However, as mentioned earlier, the pressure range in which this pump operates is at the limits of our hypotheses so that a large overestimation of the flow and pressure values can be presumed.

Fig. 37: Results of the 1-D model for the secondary throughput and the critical backing pressure as function of the primary pressure. Primary nozzle throat of 50 mm, secondary inlet pressure of 10 Pa. The black solid line is the maximum throughput required by our system.

Comparison with the FVM approach

In order to improve the predictions made by the 1-D model, it was decided to carry out FVM simulations to determine efficiency factors on backing pressure and throughput. Since it is believed that the efficiency is worst at low pressure (which will be validated later), we decided to perform our simulations at low pressure in order to remain conservative in determining these efficiencies. A minimum pressure of 500 Pa, the approximate mercury operating pressure of the diffusion pumps, was chosen as this appears in Fig. 37 to be a suitable operating point. It seems unnecessary to go below this pressure, as the backing pressure is already in the desired low-pressure range.

A first simulation with a backing pressure of 10.5 Pa was performed in order to compare the mass flow rates in critical regimes (a compression factor very close to 1, ensures a critical regime as depicted in Fig. 10). Summaries of the results can be found in [Tab. 6](#) and the detailed results in the Appendix 6 and Appendix 8. Although for the primary flow rate, the results are very close to the those one can compute from the 1-D equation 4.2-1 (0.09% relative error), the secondary mass flow rate is well below the estimate from the 1-D simulation. An efficiency of our 1-D model on the secondary mass flow rate (which correspond to the secondary mass flow rate computed by FVM over the secondary mass flow rate computed by 1-D model) can be calculated at about $\eta_{ms}=0.32$. A new simulation was performed at 20 Pa backing pressure (compression ratio of 2). At this pressure, it can be seen from the decrease of the secondary mass flow rate that we are in the vicinity of the critical point. Thus, a second 1-D model efficiency on the value of this critical pressure (critical backing pressure computed by FVM over the critical backing pressure computed by 1-D model) of about $\eta_{pcb}=0.28$ can be calculated.

Tab. 6: Secondary mass flow rates and throughput for primary inlet pressure of 500 Pa and secondary inlet pressure of 10 Pa.

	Secondary mass flow rates [kg s ⁻¹]	Throughput [Pa m ³ s ⁻¹]
FVM simulation with 10.5 Pa backing pressure	2.673E-5	16.1
FVM simulation with 20 Pa backing pressure	2.585E-5	15.6
1-D simulation	8.2443E-5	49.7

1-D simulation integrating the efficiencies

One can think (and it will be demonstrated later) that the predictive efficiencies on the secondary fluid of the 1-D model are increasing (or in the worst-case stagnating) with the increase of the different pressures. Thus, integrating the previously calculated efficiencies and performing a new 1-D simulation, we obtain the results shown in [Fig. 38](#). It can be seen that a primary pressure of 1500 Pa would allow us to achieve our minimum objective of a 50 Pa backing pressure in one stage. Achieving this backing pressure in one stage limits the throughput to 1.5 Pa m³ s⁻¹, which means 6 ejector pumps i.e. 2 ejectors per diffusion pumps which, using a positioning as shown in [Fig. 39](#), would appear not to be an insurmountable problem. The required power per ejector can then be estimated from the mercury mass flow rate. The mass flow rate follows directly from the choked flow condition in the nozzle throat (cf. equation 4.2-1) and the stagnation conditions. Assuming a constant vaporization enthalpy of 310 kJ kg⁻¹ [68] this yields a power of around 1.67 kW per ejector (so a total of around 10 kW for the 6 ejectors and 100kW for the all tokamak).

Fig. 38: Results of the 1-D model including the efficiencies for the throughput and the critical backing pressure as function of the primary pressure. Primary nozzle throat of 50 mm, secondary inlet pressure of 10 Pa.

Fig. 39: Positioning of ejector pumps (green) to diffusion pumps (purple).

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FVM validation of the INTL first stage ejector pump

As expected, the prediction error decreases with increasing primary pressure. Thus, in order to validate our previously defined operating point at 1500 Pa, we calculated using the FVM method the ejector with a primary pressure of 1500 Pa and found a throughput of $1.6 \text{ Pa m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ (complete results in Appendix 9 and Appendix 10). This value is higher than the predictions of the 1-D model with efficiency factors that predicted a flow rate of $1.48 \text{ Pa m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$. This validates our earlier assumption that efficiencies increase with pressure and confirms that the realised sizing is conservative.

Conclusion on INTL first stage ejector pump

In view of the results presented above, we can guarantee a minimum compression ratio of 5 i.e. to a minimum backing pressure of 50 Pa which is in the target range. The achievement of this objective in its lower part, is certainly a disadvantage with respect to the final objective but allows in the case where the MFPS only discharge at 50 Pa in the DURL to be able to use the same solutions (detailed in the following section) as in the INTL. Thus, the work presented will cover all possible pressure ranges.

5.3 Sizing of the 6-pack ejector pump

Using the ejector proportions determined above, and based on the desired final size in order to fit in a commercial glovebox, we can determine a primary nozzle diameter of approximately 10 mm. In order to allow for semi-series production, we decided to use the same size for all ejectors. Using the 1-D model with the efficiencies computed for the first stage (see above), we are able to predict (in a very conservative way) the rough number of pumps needed. A typical example of such an analysis is shown on [Tab. 7](#). The power are computed in the same way as above

First of all, let us recall that the problem is a multifactor optimisation problem. For the results presented, and remembering that the aim is to demonstrate the possibility of using ejectors, only the pressures and throughput (in order to obtain the number of pumps needed) have been studied. Typically, the heating power for the primary fluid is only an informative output that has not been considered in the optimisation here. With this in mind, it can first be noted that using ejectors may be a viable solution. Furthermore, we must remember that it is likely that the efficiencies used to dimension this problem were calculated under very low-pressure conditions and that these may increase with primary and secondary pressure. A FVM simulation based on the first stage has been made to confirm it. Their results are available in Appendix 11. It appears that a throughput of $3.74 \text{ Pa m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ instead of $3.3 \text{ Pa m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ is found, reflecting thus a better efficiency. This confirms once again that the results found are conservative.

Indeed, it can be seen that with a total of 53 packs, the minimum target pressure can be reached. By adding only two packs, the pressure of 900 Pa could be reached, which would allow the number of LRPs to be reduced significantly. The last stage presented in this table is purely informative. It can be believed regarding the particularly impressive performances that we are at the limits of the predictions of our model. It should be noted, however, that the power increases with each stage and that the power required for the last stages is significant and therefore calls for discussion with regard to the other solutions and the overall objectives. In addition, it was assumed that between each stage, the primary fluid was completely liquefied and therefore the secondary fluid was cooled to 20°C. The liquefaction of the secondary fluid has not been studied here and may represent a problem with regard to the powers involved.

Tab. 7: Possible realization of a pumping system based on ejectors modelled by the 1-D simulation.

Property	Stage 1	Stage 2	Stage 3	Stage 4	Stage 5					
Inlet pressure [Pa]	50	100	300	900	1700	3950	6500	9880	14800	22000
Primary nozzle diameter [mm]	10	10	10	10	10					
Primary pressure [Pa]	2500	8250	24000	35000	90000					
Primary temperature [K]	475	512	550	565	607					
Primary mass flow rate [kg s ⁻¹]	0.00101	0.00322	0.00905	0.01303	0.03232					
Power per ejector [kW]	0.31	1.00	2.81	4.04	10.02					
Backing pressure [Pa]	100	300	900	1700	3950	6500	9880	14800	22000	34000
Throughput [Pa m ³ s ⁻¹]	3.3	3.7	12	70	106	390	740	1215	1925	2975
Number ejector DURL	110	98	30	6	4	0.9230769	0.4864864	0.2962963	0.1870129	0.121008
Number ejector INTL	28	25	8	2	1	0.2307692	0.1216216	0.0740740	0.0467532	0.030252
Number pack DURL	19	17	5	1	1					
Number pack INTL	5	5	2	1	1					
Power of a pack [kW]	1.89	6.00	16.84	24.23	60.12					
Power the stage [kW]	45.27	131.91	117.85	48.46	120.25					
Cumulative number pack	24	46	53	55	57					
Cumulative power [kW]	45.27	177.18	295.03	343.49	463.74					

5.4 Sensitivity study

5.4.1 Pressure sensitivity

Primary pressure sensitivity

As shown in [Fig. 40](#) and [Fig. 41](#), the pump parameters are strongly dependant on the primary pressure. Thus, the choice of the primary pressure is very important. Indeed, it is a compromise that must be made between the maximum critical pressure against which one can pump and the flow rate that will be pumped. The more gas you pump, the lower the pressure at which you can pump it. This choice is all the more complex as both curves show a very rapid growth (respectively decrease). It is therefore an optimisation problem based on the objectives to be defined.

Fig. 40: Sensitivity of the primary pressure in with a critical secondary mass flow rate point of view. Complete results are in Appendix 12.

Fig. 41: Sensitivity of the primary pressure with a critical pressure point of view. Complete results are in Appendix 12.

Secondary pressure sensitivity

Fig. 42 shows the sensitivity of the secondary mass flow rate to the secondary pressure. In contrast to the primary pressure, a nearly linear variation can be seen here as predicted in section 3.2. Thus, an increase in secondary pressure will always increase the performance of the pumping system. A design that minimises this pressure, as has been done here, is therefore very conservative and guarantees minimal pump operation.

Fig. 42: Sensitivity of the secondary pressure. Complete data in Appendix 14.

5.4.2 Geometrical Sensitivity

The diameter ratio sensitivity

As predicted in section 3.3, Fig. 43 shows a significant sensitivity of the secondary mass flow to the diameter ratio. It is important to note that the maximum does not appear to be reached for the value 3.7 as previously assumed. Thus, a modification of this parameter on the DEMO ejectors could allow a significant improvement of the pumping capacities. Further study would be required to confirm or deny this.

Fig. 43: Sensitivity of the diameter ratio. Complete results are in Appendix 16.

NXP sensitivity

We notice on the [Fig. 44](#) curve that the variation of the throughput is highly dependent on the value of the NXP. It can be seen that there is a maximum. In view of the strong variation around this maximum, we can say that an optimisation of this parameter is essential when designing such an ejector. It should also be kept in mind that such a maximum is probably also dependent on the thermodynamic boundary conditions. A study in this sense should therefore be considered.

Fig. 44: NXP sensitivity. Complete results are in Appendix 13.

The dimensionless mixing length sensitivity

The dimensionless mixing length sensitivity is shown in [Fig. 45](#). Although it shows a maximum, it is much less sensitive than that of the NXP. However, as with the NXP, a study to confirm or deny the interdependence of this maximum with the boundary conditions would allow a much more reliable optimisation of this type of pump.

Fig. 45: Dimensionless mixing length sensitivity. Complete results are in Appendix 15.

5.5 Discussion of potential performance improvements

5.5.1 Reducing the power consumption of the heater

In view of the power required to operate these pumps (especially in the highest-pressure range), and in order to optimise the overall efficiency of the system, it may be worthwhile to extract the heat from the pump outlet fluid, which is at a relatively high temperature and which we wish to liquefy in order to preheat the liquid mercury that will be used as the primary fluid for the pump. This can be done by a heat exchanger or a heat pump. Indeed, considering a coefficient of performance of about 3 (which is in the low range of what is commercially available), this would mean that for an electrical power consumption of 1kW, we would cool the output fluid by about 2kW and heat the input fluid by 3kW. Moreover, rather than heating the primary fluid only with an electric heater, it may be interesting to use the cooling fluid of the blankets to exploit some of its energy without the efficiency of an electric turbine. While such a solution is interesting, it cannot be unique and independent, as the system would then not be able to function for a start-up when the tokamak cooling fluid is cold. A diagram summarising all the energy transfers mentioned here has been drawn up (see Fig. 46).

Finally, a possible solution to reduce the heating power and increase the overall performance of some pumps would be not to liquefy the mercury between two compression stages. This would increase the temperature of the absorbed fluid and thus increase the performance of the pump. However, this solution has significant disadvantages, like the high dilution of helium, deuterium and tritium in the mercury, and the significant increase in the amount of mercury required.

Fig. 46: Conceptual diagram of the different ways of condensing and vaporizing mercury.

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5.5.2 Improving the geometry of the ejectors

Performing a full geometric optimization using FVM simulations will undoubtedly improve the performance of the pump. Indeed, this study has not been carried out in any way. The performance of an optimized pump can increase significantly (more than 10% in case [29]). In literature, more than 20 geometry parameters have been investigated [69], [70]. The developed numerical tool will for sure serve very helpful to identify the geometry elements with strongest impact for the specific DEMO case application.

Some improvements of the primary nozzle that might be worthwhile to study during the further optimization of the DEMO ejector pumps are:

- Using multiple primary nozzles in parallel. Several studies such as [72–74, 74, 75] tend to show that this can increase the overall performance of the pump. Investigating such a possibility could improve performance and thus reduce the overall number of pumps.
- Adding a swirl to the primary flow. From the results of [76, 77], it seems that adding such a swirl phenomenon in the primary nozzle can significantly increase the performance of the ejector. This idea could be a serious way to improve the performance of the pump without affecting the pressure and temperature values and keeping the overall size of the current pumps.
- Non-circular nozzles (see Fig. 47) could be investigated. These could improve the performance of the pump, but more importantly also reduce the overall size of the pump [78].

Fig. 47: Different shapes of nozzle. Taken from [78].

5.5.3 Cool directly the ejector pump walls

It can be assumed that by cooling the flow directly in the diffuser, pumping performance can be improved. A trial was carried out to check whether this solution could be viable. Indeed, an improvement of about 12.4% was observed by cooling the walls of the diffuser to 300K (complete results available in Appendix 17 to Appendix 20). A better solution could be obtained by cooling at a lower temperature or, better still, by cooling through the centre of the diffuser, where the highest temperature is located. However, this must not impede the flow (which would considerably reduce the performance of the pump) and must be compatible with the overall geometry of our ejectors which must be small and already include a mercury condenser.

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6 Summary and Conclusion

An operational fusion power plant such as DEMO does require a continuous pumping system. To do so, a series arrangement of different pumps working with mercury, in order to be tritium compatible, is studied. To reach very low pressures, linear diffusion pumps (LDP) can be used. They are supported by liquid ring pumps (LRP) which operate at higher pressures (up to 10^5 Pa). However, a pressure gap exists between the maximum pressure at which a LDP can pump against (around 10 Pa) and the ultimate vacuum pressure achievable by LRPs (around 400 Pa). In order to bridge this gap, a new type of pump could be used: ejectors. The purpose of this study was to demonstrate if such a pump can be used as an intermediate, mercury-powered pumping stage and what size (approximately) it would require.

In order to answer this problem, we first looked at what models already exist in the literature. The study revealed that two methods are commonly used: (i) one-dimensional models based on shock wave and isentropic equations, and (ii) highly detailed models based on the finite volume method (FVM).

Expanding from one-dimensional modelling in the literature (all based on ejectors operating with a single fluid which is usually steam), we have developed a new improved one-dimensional model that allowed us to simulate our unique case: pumping a light element using the much heavier mercury vapour. To do this, we developed a new method to calculate the performance of an ejector when the pumped fluid sucked is not choking. Furthermore, the one-dimensional model was extended by a mixing law.

However, this one-dimensional modelling has some limitations. The first is the isentropic assumption (apart from the shockwave) which does not consider energy losses (especially turbulence). This can partially be mitigated by integrating efficiency factors. However, other points remain open: on the one hand, the strong sensitivity of this model to the diameter ratio (which was determined in our case on the basis of literature data) and on the other hand, in a less constraining but more fundamental way, the fact that no rigorous demonstration has been produced to justify the stopping condition of the new model (which has become an iterative model). Obviously, the limitations inherent in its one-dimensional property (such as the assumption of uniform velocities in the entire cross-section) must also be kept in mind. We have further assumed that the primary fluid first creates a thermodynamic throat that accelerates the second one without mixing and then after a certain point, that the mixing is perfect. A more detailed description of the mixing of the two fluids could improve the results considerably. However, this present study demonstrates, as far as possible compared with other simulations and verified with the few existing experiments taken from the literature, that we can exhaustively and accurately simulate ejectors (even in case of mixtures) with CFD based simulations.

To ensure a final verification on the suitability to simulate a mixture ejector pump based on mercury, the only case of a mercury pump found in the literature was replicated. The quantitative agreement of the new 1-D and the FVM simulation is allowing a final and complete validation.

Moreover, we have also demonstrated that in the case of mercury where the latter is liquefied at the ejector outlet in order to recover only the pumped gas, the liquefaction of the mercury did not modify much the outlet pressure of the ejector. Thus, we have simplified and restricted the future simulations to the simple ejector without taking into account the liquefaction part.

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For the application in DEMO, we first used the 1-D model to give a first prediction. We were then able to use FVM simulations to determine performance coefficients that we integrated into the 1-D model. In this way, we were able to loop back to predict more realistically the performance, although still on the conservative side.

We were then able to demonstrate that the mercury ejector pump is indeed a possible solution to complete the continuous pumping system of DEMO. Thus, 6 primary stage ejectors and about 35 ejector packs seem to be sufficient to pump the entire torus in the specified pressure range. However, we have also shown that for the high-pressure stages, the power required to operate the pumps is non-negligible.

Using the FVM method, we also made a geometrical and boundary condition sensitivity check. This sensitivity study shows that the pressure and geometrical parameters are well in agreement with possible predictions made by the literature study. Especially on the geometrical sensitivities, most of the parameters present a maximum. Working at this maximum will greatly improve the efficiency and performance of the pumping system.

Finally, in order to obtain the most efficient and effective pump design, some additional improvement possibilities have been proposed as exploiting the swirl phenomenon, or changing the number of the primary nozzle.

In conclusion, there are still many points remaining for improvement, optimisation and discussion before a fully functional pumping system can be achieved. The developed 1-D model is considered to be a helpful tool. In order to support these decisions and to reduce it to a manageable optimisation problem which still considers all the relevant parameters, their limits and priority over each other. In order to make the results as realistic as possible, it is worth recommending that more numerical simulations be carried out to determine efficiencies. In order to guarantee a perfect viability, these should be supported by experiments. From there, and considering the space, the admissible pressures and temperatures but also the capacity of vaporization and condensation of mercury as well as the required power, the final decisions could be taken.

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7 Literature

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Appendix

Appendix 1: Iterative 1-D model results for the experiment from [34]

Tab. A1-1: Iterative 1-D model results for the experiment from [34].

P _{po} [Pa]	T _{po} [K]	P _{so} [Pa]	T _{so} [K]	d _m [mm]	d _t [mm]	Entrainment ratio 1-D	Experimental entrainment ratio	Error
604000	368.15	40000	281.15	9.2	2.82	0.47858721	0.4377	9.34%
604000	368.15	40000	281.15	8.84	2.82	0.41816401	0.3937	6.21%
604000	368.15	40000	281.15	8.1	2.64	0.3878042	0.3457	12.18%
604000	368.15	40000	281.15	8.54	2.82	0.370049	0.3505	5.58%
604000	368.15	40000	281.15	7.6	2.64	0.30595365	0.2814	8.73%
604000	368.15	40000	281.15	8.1	2.82	0.30329935	0.2902	4.51%
604000	368.15	40000	281.15	7.6	2.82	0.23313888	0.2273	2.57%
604000	368.15	40000	281.15	7.34	2.64	0.26610372	0.2552	4.27%
604000	368.15	40000	281.15	7.34	2.82	0.19918532	0.2053	-2.98%
604000	368.15	40000	281.15	6.7	2.64	0.17632829	0.1859	-5.15%
538000	363.15	40000	281.15	8.1	2.64	0.45619898	0.4446	2.61%
538000	363.15	40000	281.15	7.6	2.64	0.3639998	0.3488	4.36%
538000	363.15	40000	281.15	7.34	2.64	0.31897637	0.304	4.93%
538000	363.15	40000	281.15	6.98	2.64	0.26007443	0.2718	-4.31%
538000	363.15	40000	281.15	6.7	2.64	0.21712903	0.2246	-3.33%
465000	357.15	40000	281.15	8.1	2.64	0.55555735	0.5387	3.13%
465000	357.15	40000	281.15	7.6	2.64	0.44859966	0.4241	5.78%
465000	357.15	40000	281.15	7.34	2.64	0.39625538	0.3883	2.05%
465000	357.15	40000	281.15	6.98	2.64	0.32756407	0.3117	5.09%
465000	357.15	40000	281.15	6.7	2.64	0.27730281	0.288	-3.71%
400000	351.15	40000	281.15	8.1	2.64	0.67559465	0.6227	8.49%
400000	351.15	40000	281.15	7.6	2.64	0.55121386	0.4889	12.75%
400000	351.15	40000	281.15	7.34	2.64	0.49019131	0.4393	11.58%
400000	351.15	40000	281.15	6.98	2.64	0.40995938	0.3922	4.53%
400000	351.15	40000	281.15	6.7	2.64	0.35105417	0.3257	7.78%
604000	368.15	47000	285.15	8.84	2.82	0.52256896	0.4989	4.74%
604000	368.15	47000	285.15	8.54	2.82	0.46577427	0.4048	15.06%
604000	368.15	47000	285.15	8.1	2.64	0.48675399	0.4541	7.19%
604000	368.15	47000	285.15	7.34	2.64	0.34260374	0.3503	-2.20%
604000	368.15	47000	285.15	7.6	2.82	0.30335596	0.304	-0.21%
604000	368.15	47000	285.15	6.7	2.64	0.23539247	0.235	0.17%
538000	363.15	47000	285.15	8.1	2.64	0.56822665	0.5422	4.80%
538000	363.15	47000	285.15	7.34	2.64	0.40606339	0.4034	0.66%
538000	363.15	47000	285.15	6.7	2.64	0.28490118	0.2946	-3.29%
465000	357.15	47000	285.15	8.1	2.64	0.68625073	0.635	8.07%
465000	357.15	47000	285.15	7.34	2.64	0.4984768	0.479	4.07%
465000	357.15	47000	285.15	6.7	2.64	0.35749649	0.3398	5.21%
400000	351.15	47000	285.15	8.1	2.64	0.82850572	0.7412	11.78%
400000	351.15	47000	285.15	7.34	2.64	0.61040023	0.6132	-0.46%

$$*\text{error} = \frac{\text{Entrainment ratio 1-D} - \text{Experimental entrainment ratio}}{\text{Experimental entrainment ratio}}$$

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Appendix 2: Demonstration of the mixing gas law

The heat capacity ratio is defined as:

$$\gamma = \frac{c_P}{c_V} \quad \text{A2-1}$$

And the relation of Mayer which holds for ideal gases states [79]:

$$c_P = c_V + R^* \quad \text{A2-2}$$

With R^* the specific gas law constant:

$$R^* = \frac{R}{M} \quad \text{A2-3}$$

With R the universal molar gas constant and M the molar mass.

For an ideal mixture, we define the mixture molar mass and the mixture isochoric specific heat:

$$\bar{M} = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \cdot M_i \quad \text{A2-4}$$

$$\bar{c}_V = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \cdot c_{V_i} \quad \text{A2-5}$$

It comes then:

$$\bar{R}^* = \frac{R}{\bar{M}} = \frac{R}{\sum x_i \cdot M_i} = \frac{1}{\sum \frac{x_i}{R_i^*}} \quad \text{A2-6}$$

And from the relation of Mayer it comes:

$$\frac{c_V}{R^*} = \frac{1}{\gamma-1} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{c_P}{R^*} = \frac{\gamma}{\gamma-1} \quad \text{A2-7}$$

And for two species i and j :

$$\frac{c_{V_i}}{R_j^*} = \frac{c_{V_i} M_j}{R} = \frac{c_{V_i} M_i M_j}{R M_i} = \frac{c_{V_i}}{R_i^*} \cdot \frac{M_j}{M_i} = \frac{1}{\gamma_i - 1} \frac{M_j}{M_i} \quad \text{A2-8}$$

So, for a mixture of n gases the Mayer relation gives us:

$$\bar{c}_P = \bar{c}_V + \bar{R}^* = \quad \text{A2-9}$$

So, by definition it comes:

$$\bar{\gamma} = \frac{\bar{c}_P}{\bar{c}_V} = \frac{\bar{c}_V + \bar{R}^*}{\bar{c}_V} = 1 + \frac{\bar{R}^*}{\bar{c}_V} \quad \text{A2-10}$$

$$= 1 + \frac{\frac{1}{\sum \frac{x_i}{R_i^*}}}{\sum x_i \cdot c_{V_i}} \quad \text{A2-11}$$

$$= 1 + \frac{1}{\left(\sum \frac{x_i}{R_i^*}\right) \left(\sum x_j \cdot c_{V_j}\right)} \quad \text{A2-12}$$

$$= 1 + \frac{1}{\sum \sum x_i x_j \frac{c_{V_i}}{R_j^*}} \quad \text{A2-13}$$

$$= 1 + \frac{1}{\sum \sum \frac{x_i x_j M_j}{\gamma - 1 M_i}} \quad \text{A2-14}$$

Appendix 3: Iterative 1-D model results with mixing law for the experiment from [49]

+ Experimental data ♦ 1D model data

Nozzle Diameter: 4.03 mm
CO₂ mass fraction: 0 %

+ Experimental data ♦ 1D model data

Nozzle Diameter: 4.03 mm
CO₂ mass fraction: 21 %

+ Experimental data ♦ 1D model data

Nozzle Diameter: 4.23 mm
CO₂ mass fraction: 0 %

+ Experimental data ♦ 1D model data

Nozzle Diameter: 4.23 mm
CO₂ mass fraction: 23 %

+ Experimental data ♦ 1D model data

Nozzle Diameter: 4.59 mm
CO₂ mass fraction: 0 %

+ Experimental data ♦ 1D model data

Nozzle Diameter: 4.59 mm
CO₂ mass fraction: 27 %

+ Experimental data ♦ 1D model data

Nozzle Diameter: 5.09 mm
CO₂ mass fraction: 0 %

+ Experimental data ♦ 1D model data

Nozzle Diameter: 5.09 mm
CO₂ mass fraction: 30 %

Fig. A3-1: Comparison of the experimental data from [49] with the improved 1-D model developed in this thesis.

Appendix 4: Different diameter ratios from the literature.

Tab. A4-1: Different diameter ratios from the literature.

gas	d_t [mm]	d_m [mm]	τ	Reference
mercury/air	4.54	11	2.42290749	[70]
CO2	2	4	2	[28]
R134a	2	4.8	2.4	[40, 41]
R134a	1	2.4	2.4	[80]
R134a	1	2.88	2.88	[80]
R134a	1	1.92	1.92	[80]
R141b	2.64	6.7	2.53787879	[34]
R141b	2.64	6.98	2.64393939	[34]
R141b	2.64	7.34	2.78030303	[34]
R141b	2.64	7.6	2.87878788	[34]
R141b	2.64	8.1	3.06818182	[34]
R141b	2.82	7.34	2.60283688	[34]
R141b	2.82	7.6	2.69503546	[34]
R141b	2.82	8.1	2.87234043	[34]
R141b	2.82	8.54	3.02836879	[34]
R141b	2.82	8.84	3.13475177	[34]
R141b	2.82	9.2	3.26241135	[34]
steam	2	19	9.5	[81]
steam	2.3	19	8.26086957	[81]
steam	1.5	13.4	8.93333333	[81]
steam	1.7	13.4	7.88235294	[81]
steam	2	19	9.5	[81]
steam	1.5	13.4	8.93333333	[81]
steam	2.63	15.8	6.00760456	[61]
steam	2	19	9.5	[38, 39]
steam	1.75	19	10.8571429	[38, 39]
steam	1.5	19	12.6666667	[38, 39]
steam	4.03	9.5	2.3573201	[49]
steam	4.23	9.5	2.24586288	[49]
steam	4.59	9.5	2.06971678	[49]
steam	5.09	9.5	1.86640472	[49]
air/air	6.07	27	4.44810544	[82]
air/air	2.54	10.16	4	[33]
air/air	2.54	15.24	6	[33]
air/air	2.54	25.4	10	[33]
air/air	5.08	10.16	2	[33]
air/air	5.08	15.24	3	[33]
air/air	5.08	25.4	5	[33]

Appendix 5: Typical example of a 6-ejector pack

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Fig. A5-1: Typical example of a 6-ejector pack.

Fig. A5-2: detail view of the primary nozzle part.

Fig. A5-3: detail view of the mixing part.

Appendix 6: FVM Results for $P_{p0}=500 \text{ Pa}$; $P_{s0}=10 \text{ Pa}$ $P_c=10.5 \text{ Pa}$

Tab. A6-1: geometrical parameters.

Nozzle diameter: 50 mm
Diameter ratio: 3.7
Dimensionless mixing length: 2
NXP: 20 mm

Tab. A6-2: mass flow rate results [kg s^{-1}].

Primary inlet	0.004761662
Secondary inlet	2.673783E-5
Outlet	-0.004788401
Mass conservation	-7.952243E-10

Fig. A6-1: Results for the static pressure.

Fig. A6-2: Results for the static temperature.

Fig. A6-3: Results for the molar concentration of helium.

Fig. A6-4: Results for the Mach number.

Fig. A6-5: Results for the density.

Fig. A6-6: Results for the velocity.

Appendix 7: FVM Results for $P_{p0}=500$ Pa; $P_{s0}=10$ Pa $P_c=15$ Pa

Tab. A7-1: geometrical parameters.

Nozzle diameter: 50 mm
Diameter ratio: 3.7
Dimensionless mixing length: 2
NXP: 20 mm

Tab. A7-2: mass flow rate results [$kg\ s^{-1}$].

Primary inlet	0.00476166198
Secondary inlet	2.67043199E-5
Outlet	-0.0047883664
Mass conservation	-5.02E-11

Fig. A7-1: Results for the static pressure.

Fig. A7-2: Results for the static temperature.

Fig. A7-3: Results for the molar fraction of helium.

Fig. A7-4: Results for the Mach number.

Fig. A7-5: Results for the density.

Fig. A7-6: Results for the velocity.

Appendix 8: FVM Results for $P_{p0}=500$ Pa; $P_{s0}=10$ Pa $P_c=20$ Pa

Tab. A8-1: geometrical parameters.

Nozzle diameter: 50 mm
Diameter ratio: 3.7
Dimensionless mixing length: 2
NXP: 20 mm

Tab. A8-2: mass flow rate results [$kg\ s^{-1}$].

Primary inlet	0.00476166
Secondary inlet	2.59E-05
Outlet	-0.00478752
Mass conservation	-5.90E-11

Fig. A8-1: Results for the static pressure.

Fig. A8-2: Results for the static temperature.

Fig. A8-3: Results for the molar fraction of helium.

Fig. A8-4: Results for the Mach number.

Fig. A8-5: Results for the density.

Fig. A8-6: Results for the velocity.

Appendix 9: FVM Results for $P_{p0}=1500$ Pa; $P_{s0}=10$ Pa $P_c=10.5$ Pa

Tab. A9-1: geometrical parameters.

Nozzle diameter: 50 mm
Diameter ratio: 3.7
Dimensionless mixing length: 2
NXP: 20 mm

Tab. A9-2: mass flow rate results [$kg\ s^{-1}$].

Primary inlet	0.01420964
Secondary inlet	2.96E-06
Outlet	-0.0142126
Mass conservation	4.42E-09

Fig. A9-1: Results for the static pressure.

Fig. A9-2: Results for the static temperature.

Fig. A9-3: Results for the molar fraction of helium.

Fig. A9-4: Results for the Mach number.

Fig. A9-5: Results for the density.

Fig. A9-6: Results for the velocity.

Appendix 10: FVM Results for $P_{p0}=500$ Pa; $P_{s0}=10$ Pa $P_c=50$ Pa

Tab. A10-1: geometrical parameters.

Nozzle diameter: 50 mm
Diameter ratio: 3.7
Dimensionless mixing length: 2
NXP: 20 mm

Tab. A10-2: mass flow rate results [$kg\ s^{-1}$].

Primary inlet	0.01420964
Secondary inlet	3.01E-06
Outlet	-0.01421263
Mass conservation	9.20E-09

Fig. A10-1: Results for the static pressure.

Fig. A10-2: Results for the static temperature.

Fig. A10-3: Results for the molar fraction of helium.

Fig. A10-4: Results for the Mach number.

Fig. A10-5: Results for the density.

Fig. A10-6: Results for the velocity.

Appendix 11: Simulation of the first stage ($P_{p0}=2500$ Pa; $P_{s0}=50$ Pa $P_c=100$ Pa) of the pack ejectors

Tab. A11-1: geometrical parameters.

Nozzle diameter: 10 mm
Diameter ratio: 3.7
Dimensionless mixing length: 2
NXP: 2 mm

Tab. A11-2: mass flow rate results [$kg s^{-1}$].

Primary inlet	0.000990841
Secondary inlet	6.11E-06
Outlet	-0.000990841
Mass conservation	5.20E-10

Fig. 48: Results for the static pressure.

Fig. A11-2: Results for the static temperature.

Fig. A11-3: Results for the molar fraction of helium.

Fig. A11-4: Results for the Mach number.

Fig. A11-5: Results for the density.

Fig. A11-6: Results for the velocity.

Appendix 12: Primary pressure sensitivity results

The Geometry used is the 50mm primary throat ejector. The global results are given in the followings tables

Tab. A12-1: Primary pressure sensitivity results.

P_{p0} [Pa]	P_{s0} [Pa]	P_{cb} [Pa]	m_p [kg s ⁻¹]	m_s [kg s ⁻¹]	out [kg s ⁻¹]	mass conservation [kg s ⁻¹]	entrainment ratio
500	10	15	0.004761	2.67E-05	-0.00478837	-5.02E-11	5.61E-03
500	10	10.5	0.004761	2.67E-05	-0.0047884	-7.95E-10	5.62E-03
500	10	20	0.004761	2.59E-05	-0.00478752	-5.90E-11	5.43E-03
500	10	25	0.004761	1.77E-05	-0.00477933	-8.81E-11	3.71E-03
500	10	22	0.004761	2.43E-05	-0.00478594	6.58E-09	5.10E-03
1500	10	10.5	0.014209	2.96E-06	-0.0142126	4.42E-09	2.08E-04
1500	10	50	0.014209	3.01E-06	-0.01421263	9.20E-09	2.12E-04
1500	10	52	0.014209	1.38E-06	-0.01421102	-1.15E-09	9.71E-05
1500	10	55	0.014209	1.21E-06	-0.01421085	-1.84E-09	8.50E-05
1000	10	10.5	0.014382	3.37E-06	-0.01438564	9.52E-08	2.34E-04
1000	10	40	0.014382	3.36E-06	-0.01438552	1.98E-07	2.33E-04
1000	10	45	0.014382	3.30E-06	-0.01438585	-1.91E-07	2.29E-04
1000	10	50	0.009443	1.54E-06	-0.00944492	3.67E-08	1.63E-04

Appendix 13: NXP sensitivity results

Tab. A13-1: NXP sensitivity results.

NXP variation	sec mass flow	Throughput [Pa m ³ s ⁻¹]	primary mass flow	NXP [mm]	Throughput variation
1	6.70E-05	5.77193175	0.00270333	26.3055216	1
1.5	2.59E-04	22.3458971	0.00270721	35.7658764	3.87147632
1.75	2.75E-04	23.6608013	0.00271048	39.9092916	4.0992864
2	2.62E-04	2.25E+01	0.00271007	43.7708387	3.90280805
3	1.81E-04	15.5475333	0.00270469	57.2346782	2.69364469
4	1.03E-04	8.88888489	0.00270532	68.6064382	1.54001906

Appendix 14: Secondary inlet pressure sensitivity results

Tab. A14-1: Secondary pressure sensitivity results.

P_{p0} [Pa]	P_{s0} [Pa]	P_c [Pa]	m_p [kg s ⁻¹]	m_s [kg s ⁻¹]	out [kg s ⁻¹]	mass conservation [kg s ⁻¹]	entrainment ratio
1000	10	10.5	0.01438236	3.37E-06	-0.01438564	9.52E-08	2.34E-04
1000	10	40	0.01438236	3.36E-06	-0.01438552	1.98E-07	2.33E-04
1000	10	45	0.01438236	3.30E-06	-0.01438585	-1.91E-07	2.29E-04
1000	10	50	0.00944341	1.54E-06	-0.00944492	3.67E-08	1.63E-04
1000	15	16	0.00944362	3.55E-05	-0.00947904	9.86E-08	3.76E-03
1000	15	40	0.00944362	3.55E-05	-0.009479	1.07E-07	3.76E-03
1000	15	45	0.00944335	2.94E-05	-0.00947288	-1.13E-07	3.12E-03
1000	20	22	0.00944479	5.35E-05	-0.00949856	-2.55E-07	5.67E-03
1000	20	40	0.00944345	5.32E-05	-0.0094967	-1.92E-08	5.64E-03
1000	20	45	0.0094436	3.12E-05	-0.00947485	-3.08E-08	3.31E-03

Appendix 15: Sensitivity of the dimensionless mixing length

Tab. A15-1: Sensitivity of the dimensionless mixing length.

P_{p0} [Pa]	P_{s0} [Pa]	P_c [Pa]	length ratio	m_p [kg/s]	m_s [kg/s]	out [kg/s]	mass conservation [kg/s]
1000	15	35	2	0.00944362	3.55E-05	-0.009479	1.07E-07
1000	15	35	1	0.0094369	3.66E-05	-0.00947348	3.82E-08
1000	15	35	3	0.00941377	1.77E-05	-0.00943147	4.90E-09
1000	15	35	0	0.00946435	3.10E-05	-0.00949548	-1.20E-07

Appendix 16: Sensitivity of the diameter ratio

Tab. A16-1: Sensitivity of the diameter ratio.

P_{p0} [Pa]	P_{s0} [Pa]	P_c [Pa]	diameter ratio	m_p [kg/s]	m_s [kg/s]	out [kg/s]
1000	15	35	3	0.00949602	9.34E-06	-0.00950533
1000	15	35	3.3	0.00946582	2.59E-05	-0.00949204
1000	15	35	3.5	0.00944362	3.55E-05	-0.009479
1000	15	35	3.7	0.00941464	2.05E-05	-0.00943513
1000	15	35	3.9	0.00942638	4.82E-05	-0.00947462
1000	15	35	4.5	0.0093631	2.98E-05	-0.00939307

Appendix 17: Cooling ejector walls simulations

Tab. A17-1: Cooling ejector walls simulations.

Case	P_{p0} [Pa]	P_{s0} [Pa]	P_c [Pa]	m_p [kg/s]	m_s [kg/s]	out [kg s ⁻¹]	mass conservation [kg s ⁻¹]	variation
reference	1000	20	40	0.009443	5.32E-05	-0.00949	-1.92E-08	
diffuser cooled	1000	20	40	0.009443	5.98E-05	-0.009503	2.32E-08	12.40%
diffuser and mixing chamber cooled	1000	20	40	0.009443	5.68E-05	-0.00950	8.87E-10	6.68%
mixing chamber cooled	1000	20	40	0.009443	5.62E-05	-0.00949	1.71E-08	5.66%

Appendix 18: Cooling ejector diffuser wall

Tab. A18-1: geometrical parameters.

Nozzle diameter: 50 mm
Diameter ratio: 3.7
Dimensionless mixing length: 2
NXP: 20 mm

Fig. A18-1: Results for the static pressure.

Fig. A18-2: Results for the static temperature.

Fig. A18-3: Results for the molar fraction of helium.

Fig. A18-4: Results for the Mach number.

Fig. A18-5: Results for the density.

Fig. A18-6: Results for the velocity.

Appendix 19: Cooling ejector diffuser and mixing chamber walls

Tab. A17-2: geometrical parameters.

Nozzle diameter: 50 mm
Diameter ratio: 3.7
Dimensionless mixing length: 2
NXP: 20 mm

Fig. A19-1: Results for the static pressure.

Fig. A19-2: Results for the static temperature.

Fig. A19-3: Results for the molar fraction of helium.

Fig. A19-4: Results for the Mach number.

Fig. A19-5: Results for the density.

Fig. A19-6: Results for the velocity.

Appendix 20: Cooling ejector mixing chamber wall

Tab. A20-2: geometrical parameters.

Nozzle diameter: 50 mm
Diameter ratio: 3.7
Dimensionless mixing length: 2
NXP: 20 mm

Fig. A20-1: Results for the static pressure.

Fig. A20-2: Results for the static temperature.

Fig. A20-3: Results for the molar fraction of helium.

Fig. A20-4: Results for the Mach number.

Fig. A20-5: Results for the density.

Fig. A20-6: Results for the velocity.